

D4.6

Legal and Ethical Guidelines on Data Transfers and Trading (Final Version)

Law and Internet Foundation (LIF)

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Abstract

D4.6 constitutes both a revision and an elaboration of D4.5. The current text is thus not only preoccupied with excelling at presenting and analysing the principles touched upon in the previous Deliverable, but also with exploring additional topics, e.g. sectoral aspects, the role of data spaces, etc. D4.6 is of its kind also a review of the DATAMITE's Pilots, in the context of these topics.

Keywords

Data, Governance, Transfers, Trading, Legal, Ethical, Sectoral, Compliance, Interoperability.

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Nature of the deliverable

R

Dissemination level

PU Public, fully open. e.g., website

✓

CL Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

SEN Confidential to DATAMITE project and Commission Services

* Deliverable types:

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
B2B	Business-to-Business
B2C	Business-to-Consumer
B2G	Business-to-Government
DA	Data Act
DGA	Data Governance Act
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DMA	Digital Markets Act
DoA	Description of Action
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DSA	Digital Services Act
DSO	Distribution System Operators
EC	European Commission
EEA	European Economic Area
EU AI Act	European Union Artificial Intelligence Act
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability of Data
FFD	Free Flow of Non-Personal Data Directive
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
G2B	Government-to-Business
G2G	Government-to-Government
IoT	Internet of Things
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
MoSCoW	Must, Should, Could, Would
MSs	Member States
ODD	Open Data Directive
PSB	Public Sector Body
PSI	Public Sector Information
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
TSO	Transmission System Operators
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

Deliverable 4.6 offers insights and a nuanced exploration of the evolving EU data-sharing landscape, including general and sectoral legal acts & ethical principles, as well as the overall potential of new upcoming hard and soft laws.

Finally, the applied research methodology is qualitative, the data relied upon is secondary, and the narrative is an amalgam of both descriptive and analytical reasoning. To construe its interpretations and guidelines, the report relies heavily on the robust applicable EU hard and soft law sources, but also explores other scholars' experiences in the field, e.g., the recently published by Routledge, "Data Sharing Regulation in Europe" [14], which has served as an intellectual inspiration in finalising the second version of this report. In parallel to all regulatory sources, the generation of D4.6, as well as the Definition of the Legal & Ethical Requirements that are being subsequently shared shortly thereafter, have been substantially relied upon the outcomes of D1.4 Requirements and Architecture (M30), D2.4 Data Sharing and Sovereignty Mechanisms (M33), as well as the questions that have been re-confirmed with Pilot Partners.

The overall approach to the analysis and the definition of the applicable rules is thus aimed at allowing even readers who are not directly engaged with the Project, to test the interpretation and application of the regulatory norms in practical terms, and against actual scenarios, thereby developing a comprehension of the robust and complex landscape of the laws and ethics applicable to the data sharing realm.

1 Introduction

DATAMITE is a project funded by the European Commission as part of the Horizon Europe programme and coordinated by the ITI – Technological Institute of Informatics. DATAMITE empowers European companies by delivering a modular, open-source and multi-domain Framework to improve DATA Monetizing, Interoperability, Trading and Exchange, in the form of software modules, training, and business materials.

DATAMITE unleashes the monetization potential at two levels. At internal level, users will have tools to improve quality management of their data, the adherence to FAIR principles, and will be able to upskill on technical and business aspects thanks to the multiple open-source training materials the project will generate. Therefore, data will become trustable and more reliable also in other paradigms like AI.

At external level, keeping users in control of their data will provide new sources of revenue and interaction with other stakeholders. The architecture envisioned for DATAMITE enables DIHs sandboxing, becoming a potential instructor on their onboarding of SMEs and low-tech SMEs into the data economy. Together, DATAMITE's solutions will function as a catalyst to boost data monetization in the European productive fabric.

1.1 Deliverable Purpose and Scope

As it has been embedded in the Grant Agreement Amendment (No. AMD-101092989-38), D4.6 not only reflects the new technological developments within the project from legal and ethical perspectives, but the document also elaborates on sectoral legislation and the overall potential of new upcoming hard and soft laws. In addition, the tailored guidelines per the Pilots are revised and updated accordingly, thereby covering the entire timeline of the project and beyond. Furthermore, in comparison to D4.5, which has mainly outlined the roles and duties that may apply in numerous instances, D4.6 delves deeper into examining further the different concepts and principles, thereby providing a more analytical and revised approach to the data sharing & trading framework in general, but also with regard to the DATAMITE context implications.

1.2 Document Structure

This deliverable is broken down into the following sections:

- **Executive Summary:** A summary of the contents and main findings is provided.

- **Section 1 Introduction** provides the deliverable's general context, dependencies, and structure.
- **Section 2 Outline of DATAMITE Developments: Legal and Ethical Overview** outlines the most up-to-date developments of the DATAMITE modules, tools and use cases, outlining a high-level legal and ethical assessment in that regard.
- **Section 3 Applicable Data Sharing Legal Framework** carries out an in-depth analysis of the applicable regulatory framework, strictly in terms of data sharing, including a section dedicated to data spaces and sectoral regulations.
- **Section 4 Personal Data Protection and its Role in Defining the Legal Framework** concentrates on the GDPR implications and the intertwined aspects with other legal acts.
- **Section 5 Additional Applicable Legal Sources & Considerations** explores briefly other applicable legal sources which go beyond the strict data sharing per se context, e.g., Artificial Intelligence, Cybersecurity, Intellectual Property.
- **Section 6 Ethical Dimensions** discusses the applicable ethical principles concerning human participants, in general, personal data, specifically, as well as Artificial Intelligence.
- **Section 7 New European Strategy for Data** recalls the benefits of data sharing, by also sharing the views of the DATAMITE Consortium concerning the New European Strategy for Data, and more particularly, concerning the obstacles to data sharing and the need for EU Regulatory intervention.
- **Section 8 Conclusions** wraps up the essence of the aforementioned.
- **Section 9 References.**

Appendixes:

- **Appendix A** Definition of Legal & Ethical Requirements to the DATAMITE Tools.

1.3 Document Dependencies

The generation of D4.6, as well as the Definition of the Legal & Ethical Requirements that are being subsequently shared shortly thereafter, has substantially relied upon the outcomes of D1.4 Requirements and Architecture (M30), D2.4 Data Sharing and Sovereignty Mechanisms (M33), as well as the questions that have been reconfirmed with Pilot Partners.

2 Outline of DATAMITE Developments: Legal and Ethical Methodology Roadmap

2.1 Modules and Tools

The nearly 200 functional & non-functional requirements concerning the Data Governance, Data Quality, Data Sharing, Data Security, as well as Data Support Tools, which also cover Requirements related to the Management of the Platform, are to be specifically addressed in a separate sheet format. Due to the volume of the framework, once the tailored guidelines have been finalised by LIF, the same shall be shared with the Consortium separately and shortly after the submission of D4.6. It shall be up to the decision of the Coordinator (ITI) whether the same are to be public, as is the status of D4.6.

DATAMITE has been devised as a modular solution, where each of its modules can be optionally deployed by the user according to their needs. However, as D1.4 mentions, modular does not mean independent, and there exist relations, complementarities, and synergies between the modules that make every of it better in the presence of the others. This is yet another reason to acknowledge the need for providing separate tailored guidelines per requirement, rather than simply addressing the modules in general terms, as multiple legal & ethical framework are applicable per module/tool, depending on the functionality. Sometimes, even more than one legal & ethical rule exists per technical requirement.

As visualised in the column titles of Annex A, the tailored requirements guidelines are going to depict the following content: Requirement ID; Requirement Description; Actor; Source; Category; Requirement Type; Priority (based on MoSCoW, prioritisation matrix, i.e., “must”, “should”, “could” have legal & ethics requirements) [35]. Furthermore, besides the definition of the said requirements related to the main DATAMITE modules that are being defined legally and ethically, there are two more relevant aspects to be considered: the front end and the general management of the platform. The front end is not a module itself, but it provides the user interface for DATAMITE modules or the connection point between them. The guidelines are based on the final status of the architecture as presented in M30, and the same shall be attached to the overall functional & non-functional requirements form, as certain interdependencies exist. The final version of the file shall be shared with the DATAMITE Partners in January 2026.

2.2 Use Cases

The tailored guidelines concerning the Pilots have been revised and updated accordingly since D4.5, based on further consultation conducted with involved organisations concerning the final logistical aspects. The initial implications have thus been reconfirmed and modified accordingly, based on both the nature of the datasets, as well as the applicable sectors within the respective pilots, e.g., energy/electricity, telecommunications, agriculture, but also meteorological and overall data spaces implications. All forthcoming legal & ethical documents that are reviewed and analysed below address these implications further.

The DATAMITE Pilots are: Pilot 1 “Corporate Multi-Domain Data Exchange with DIH Support”; Pilot 2 “Corporate Multi-Site Data Exchange”; Pilot 3 “Offering Data to Service Providers with Dataspaces”; Pilot 4 “Leveraging Electricity Distribution Open Data”; Pilot 5 “Connecting EDWIN to Data Markets”; Pilot 6 “Connecting MISTRAL to the EU AI-ON-DEMAND Platform”.

2.3 D4.6 Goals & Subsequent Steps

The generation of D4.6, as well as the Definition of the Legal & Ethical Requirements that are being shared separately and shortly thereafter, has substantially relied upon the outcomes of D1.4 Requirements and Architecture (M30), D2.4 Data Sharing and Sovereignty Mechanisms (M33), as well as the questions that have been reconfirmed with respective Pilot and Technical Partners.

What does D4.6 (submitted in November 2025) cover to complement the former D4.5?

- Further in-depth analysis of the overall regulatory framework.
- Review of additional sectoral-related aspects.
- Updated revisions of applicability to Pilots.
- High-level comparative overview of the Framework (data types, pro-sharing objectives, tools).

What are the subsequent steps ahead (submitted/conducted in January 2026)?

- ~ 200 Functional & Non-Functional Requirements Rulebook Methodology (MoSCoW).
- Pilot Documentation as per Section 6.
- Wrap-Up Guidance and Q&A Webinar Pilots (Framework & Documentation).
- Wrap-Up Guidance and Q&A Technical Partners (Framework & finalised Appendix A).

3 Applicable Data Sharing Legal Framework

Oftentimes compared to “oil” for its transformative impact on the 21st-century economy [15], in today’s digital age, data has become a crucial asset, and so has the ability to collect and analyse “Big Data” become essential for businesses seeking to enhance customer experiences, lower production costs and gain a competitive edge. The increasing importance of data is also underscored by the rapid growth of online platforms and the proliferation of Internet of Things (IoT) devices, which gather extensive data through embedded sensors [16]. This data is pivotal for training Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms, which in turn improve decision-making and operational efficiency. Enabling effective data sharing goes beyond regulatory compliance – it is a strategic necessity vital for driving innovation and economic advancement within the EU. Holding significant promise for augmenting data value, stimulating economic activity and lowering entry barriers for emerging market players, developing efficient data-sharing mechanisms is thus crucial for realising the full potential of data and fostering innovation. At the same time, challenges to effective data sharing exist, and the most prominent are with regard to interoperability issues, regulatory barriers and security concerns [17]. In addition, the lack of a robust data market creates incentive problems, as firms often struggle to assess the value of their data, which usually leads to either open access without compensation or a reluctance to share [18].

Designed to tackle these issues, the EU has introduced a new legal framework, thereby addressing this “data-sharing paradox”. This framework is comprised of two main components – the development of Common European Data Spaces to address technical, privacy and security challenges, and a suite of cross-sector legislative proposals. These regulatory pieces include numerous acts, which are being discussed below, and together, they aim to enhance data sharing across various sectors, provide legal clarity and address specific market failures and public interest concerns. The framework covers B2B, G2B and B2G.

All in all, Chapter 3 of D4.6 outlines the wholeness of the data-sharing legislative system regulating data access, transfer and sharing, both in general and on sector-specific basis, but it also points at areas of overlaps that may create problems in terms of coherence and legal certainty.

3.1 Categorisation of Data and Stakeholders in Data Sharing

Prior to delving into the different types of data and the stakeholders involved in the data sharing process, it is important to acknowledge certain common characteristics and principles first.

Constituting a non-rivalrous, multifunctional and highly dynamic resource, unlike most natural resources, data can be used simultaneously by multiple users for different purposes, thereby generating new data in the process. As traditional distinctions between public, private, personal and non-personal data are increasingly overlapping due to the blurring lines, labelling data poses challenges. At the same time, the highest value from data oftentimes arises from combining datasets from diverse sources to develop new data-oriented products and services. As data can also transition between the different categories, as it undergoes processing (e.g.: from personal to anonymised/non-personal data; from anonymised and processed private data, it may transition to public data; public sector data might be the basis for private-driven initiatives), it may also be deduced that data possesses fluid, evolving, nature, which also calls for an adaptable regulatory framework. [14]

3.1.1 Public Data

Constituting a cornerstone of modern governance and societal functioning, public data encompasses a vast array of information generated and/or collected by public entities. Referring to any data generated, compiled or maintained by public sector bodies (e.g., census data and weather forecasts, legislative records, transportation schedules, etc.), public data extends beyond mere governmental statistics, encompassing datasets generated by publicly funded research institutions, educational establishments and other entities operating in the public domain. [14]

The two central pieces of legislation that the current report shall study in this regard are the *Open Data Directive* (hereinafter “ODD”) [4] and the *Data Governance Act* (hereinafter “DGA”) [5] – with the former standing as the inaugural legislative framework establishing regulations for the re-use of public data by imposing minimum requirements on Member States (hereinafter “MS”) regarding the accessibility of public sector information (hereinafter “PSI”) for re-use, whilst the latter aiming to broaden the availability of public data for re-use by stipulating conditions for its use, particularly on instances where data is protected under, e.g., commercial confidentiality, intellectual property rights or data protection.

3.1.2 Private Data

Pertaining to information held or controlled by non-governmental entities, usually for commercial or proprietary purposes, private data encompasses a diverse range of datasets (e.g., customer records, financial transactions, proprietary algorithms, etc.), and in contrast to public data, private data is oftentimes considered confidential and requires protection against unauthorised access or disclosure. Collecting and utilising vast amounts of data to drive decision-making, enhance

operational efficiency, and gain competitive advantages, private data may thus include customer data used for targeted marketing campaigns, supply chain data optimising logistical operations, as well as research and development data fuelling innovation. Yet, as the proliferation of private data has also raised considerable ethical, legal and societal concerns (related to, e.g., data exclusivity, data security, privacy rights and algorithmic bias), as well as commodification and monetisation have sparked debates concerning consent, transparency and individual rights in the digital age – stakeholders have to navigate complex landscapes of data governance, whilst pursuing balance between innovation and economic interests, on the one hand, and privacy and consumer protection imperatives, on the other.

The three central pieces of legislation that the current report shall study in this regard, and which the European Commission (hereinafter “EC”, or “the Commission”) has launched as part of its digital and data strategies aimed at creating a thriving and inclusive European digital and data markets, include the *Digital Services Act* (hereinafter “DSA”) [3], the *Digital Markets Act* (hereinafter “DMA”) [2], as well as the *Data Act* (hereinafter “DA”) [1]. As it shall be observed later, whilst the DSA introduces uniform rules on intermediaries’ obligations and accountability across the single market, the DMA sets data-sharing obligations on large online platforms (i.e., on gatekeepers). This is done in order to reduce their exclusive control over the data they collect and decrease their market leverage, thereby eliminating market distortions within the platform, including self-reporting and information asymmetries between the platform and its commercial users, as well as distortions between competing platforms. Finally, aimed at creating an equitable data economy by ensuring access to and use of data, as well as enhancing B2B and B2G sharing mechanisms, the DA establishes opportunities for data re-use and measures for removing barriers to data sharing, promoting fair and equitable access to data and enhancing interoperability. In addition to some of its key provisions (e.g.: the increase of legal certainty for consumers and businesses accessing data from connected products and related services; the establishment of general rules for data holders obliged to make data available; addressing unfair contractual terms; as well as the defining of essential requirements for operators of data spaces to facilitate interoperability and data sharing) – the major innovation of the DA is the shift towards a binding approach, i.e., its introduction of rules requiring businesses (i.e., “data holders”) to make data available to other businesses (i.e., “data recipients”) whenever EU or domestic law requires it. As shall be studied in the subsequent pages, this concerns primarily the case of IoT data. [14]

3.1.3 Personal Data

Distinguishing between personal and non-personal data is crucial but so is acknowledging that most datasets are mixed. As shall be observed in more details later, the need to protect personal data oftentimes leads to subjecting entire mixed datasets to regulatory requirements, particularly the *General Data Protection Regulation* (hereinafter “GDPR”) [7], which is the central piece of regulation that the report studies in this regard. Pursuant to Art. 4(1) GDPR [7]:

“[...] ‘personal data’ means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person”.

Therefore, relating to an identified or identifiable living individual, the term “personal data” may also refer to different pieces of information, which when collected, can lead to the identification of a particular person and thus also constitute personal data by themselves. Personal data that has been de-identified, encrypted or pseudonymised but can still be used to re-identify a person, remains personal and is therefore still subject to the provisions of the GDPR. Including not only direct identifiers, e.g., names and addresses, but also indirect ones like IP addresses, biometric data and online identifiers, the scope of personal data thus extends to any information that, either alone, or in combination with other data, can be used to identify or distinguish an individual.

In today’s data-driven society, where personal data is permeating virtually every aspect of daily life, individuals generate vast amounts of personal data through their interactions with various digital and physical environments, and which data in return fuels targeted advertising, personalised services and decision-making processes across public and private sectors. Yet, as this vast collection and processing of personal data has raised profound concerns regarding privacy, autonomy and individual rights, in the forthcoming pages it shall be observed how organisations grappling with the complexities of personal data governance, should ensure transparency, consent and accountability, to safeguard individuals’ privacy and dignity. [14]

3.1.4 Non-Personal Data

As the definition of “non-personal data” is rather reliant on the absence of characteristics defining it as personal, giving a more precise definition is not a straightforward endeavour, which is why, the fact that a data refers to anything but personal data, usually suffices to label it as “non-personal”. Thus, constituting a category of information which is not related to or not making it possible to identify a given individual, it refers to data relating to entities, objects or phenomena

other than natural persons. Including anonymised data, aggregated data, machine-generated data, and other forms lacking personal identifiers or attributes, the scope of non-personal data is broad and diverse, and may span from datasets generated by sensors, devices, applications and automated processes, thus referring to, e.g., environmental sensor readings, traffic flow patterns, market trends, industrial data, etc. Offering valuable insights for informed decision-making and innovation, non-personal data enjoys greater flexibility in use and dissemination than personal data. Yet, responsible data stewardship and governance framework are still imperative, as ethical and societal considerations, and issues such as data quality, interoperability and algorithmic bias, may still affect the reliability and fairness of non-personal data-driven systems. [14]

On the other hand, it is crucial to recall that, both the GDPR and the *Free Flow of Non-Personal Data Regulation* (hereinafter “FFD”) [6], could potentially apply to mixed datasets containing both personal and non-personal data. However, as per Art. 2 of the GDPR, whenever personal and non-personal data are inseparably linked in a dataset, and may not be distinguished or separated, the GDPR takes precedence over the FFD, thus applying to the entire mixed dataset, even if personal data is a small or secondary fraction thereof. The concept of “inextricably linked” is not explicitly defined from a regulatory point of view, but the EC has suggested in its Guidance on the FFD, that it refers to instances where separating personal and non-personal data would be practically impossible, economically inefficient or technically unfeasible for the data controller. Therefore, it is the data controller who is largely entrusted with the power to decide on whether data are “inseparable”, thereby weighing the costs of distinguishing the data against the potential reduction in the value of resulting datasets. Respondent companies from different sectors have largely reported that separating data was likely to be costly or very costly, and as non-personal data are defined in contrast to personal data, this has led to uncertainty among business stakeholders as to what exactly is the boundary between the two. The interpretation of personal data by case law has led to further complications by making it challenging to exclude the application of the GDPR or identify rules for specific situations. Consequently, limiting the cases where FFD may apply, the GDPR makes non-personal data rare. [14] In addition to the interconnectedness with the GDPR when cumulative interpretation is required, the other central regulatory act that shall be explored with regard non-personal data is thus the FFD.

What does this interpretation mean for organisations?

As recognised by the EC, mixed datasets are generally subject to the GDPR, which entails fulfilling all obligations of data controllers and processors, as well as ensuring the rights of data

subjects, regarding any data-sharing operation involving mixed databases. This means that *both the sharing and receiving companies must ensure robust security levels for the entire dataset, pursuant to the provisions of Art. 5(f) of the GDPR*. There is still the alternative of personal data anonymisation, but this, too, requires the distinction of data and entails a cost for the data holder. Moreover, *the risk of liability in cases of incorrect anonymisation should be considered, too*. [14]

3.1.5 Stakeholders Roles

All in all, data sharing dynamics are influenced by a diverse array of stakeholders spanning across various sectors and institutional domains, and these stakeholders engage in different types of data sharing arrangements, in which unique purposes and objectives are served. The four main roles are briefly outlined. [14]

- Business-to-business (hereinafter “B2B”) data sharing concerns data exchange between commercial entities, fostering collaboration, innovation and value creation within and across industries.
- Business-to-government (hereinafter “B2G”) data sharing entails the provision of data from private sector entities to government bodies for purposes, e.g., regulatory compliance, public service delivery and policy formulation.
- Government-to-government (hereinafter “G2G”) data sharing is related to data sharing between different governmental bodies, which facilitates interagency coordination, information sharing and decision-making.
- Government-to-business (hereinafter “G2B”) data sharing refers to the Dissemination of public sector data to private entities, aimed at driving innovation, fostering transparency and supporting economic growth through giving access to businesses to valuable information resources.

3.2 General Regulations

This section deals with the interaction between general EU laws that regulate data-sharing initiatives.

3.2.1 Data Act (DA)

Intended Scope of Application

Having recently come into force in 2025, the DA applies to all industries and sectors, thus constituting a *lex generalis* (i.e., a general law applicable to a particular domain which establishes

the default legal rules), yet leaving room for sector-specific solutions for separate markets and industries (i.e., *lex specialis*). In the given context, *lex specialis* refers to additional legislative acts going beyond the DA, that implement a different equilibrium between data holders and users (i.e., between the power of platforms).

A central mission of the DA is the reference to IoT and the facilitation of access to and the use of data by consumers and businesses, at the same time preserving the incentive to invest in ways of generating value through data. For instance, if a product or service is connected through a sensor online, the DA applies. Defining what data holder is, has a very broad interpretation, as the term includes both products and services catering to IoT. As Art. 3 defines, the data holder is a legal or natural person who has the right or obligation in accordance with the law, or in the case of non-personal data and through control of the technical design of the product and related services, the ability to make available certain data. This central objective of the DA may be divided into the following subsidiary objectives. Firstly, comes the empowering consumers and business to gain more control over the usage of their IoT data, while also benefitting from more, better and cheaper products and services on secondary markets, which is to be derived from more intense competition. Secondly, in order to empower or create a level playing field both horizontally and vertically among undertakings, more data shall be available to businesses for more innovation. Thirdly, and in line with the latter, fairness in the allocation of data and the value from data among actors in the data economy. Fourthly, in parallel to adhering to the preceding, comes the preservation of incentives of manufacturers of IoT products, data holders and others to invest in ways of generating value from data. [14] Art. 3 outlines the basic structure of the DA for meeting the aforementioned objectives [1]:

“[...] products shall be designed and manufactured, and related services shall be designed and provided, in such a manner that product data and related service data, including the relevant metadata necessary to interpret and use those data, are, by default, easily, securely, free of charge, in a comprehensive, structured, commonly used and machine-readable format, and, where relevant and technically feasible, directly accessible to the user.”

Simplified Analysis of Core Provisions

The cited obligation under Art. 3 in the preceding paragraph is accompanied by a right for users to access and share the (raw) data that they have generated through their use of IoT devices (Art.4-5). This latter right under Art. 4 does not distinguish between consumers and businesses, meaning that all users of IoT devices (B2C and B2B) should be empowered by the rights and should be able to get access to all data generated by them. Pursuant to Recital 30, the user is

free to use the data for any lawful purpose, as well as pursuant to Art. 5, shall have the right to share the data generated with third parties (be that companies or other actors), with the latter being allowed to use the data for those purposes that are agreed upon with the users. Pursuant to Art. 8, the third party still needs to negotiate and enter an agreement with the data holder and is expected to pay the same fee according to Art. 9. The agreement must be concluded based on fair and reasonable terms, with the terms and conditions having to meet the requirements under Art. 8 and Art. 13, the latter stipulating a general rule against unfair contract terms. It is crucial to note that stemming from Art. 5-7, as the DA stipulates a general non-compete obligation, the user and data recipient is severely restricted to being able to compete with the data holder, and to innovate. There are also intricate rules concerning adherence to trade secret restrictions and data processing restrictions regarding personal data. What is more, the data holder is also restricted when it comes to using data in competition with third parties, as Art.5(6) reads that a data holder shall not use any readily available data to derive insights about, or the use by, the third party in any other manner that could undermine the commercial position of the same on the markets in which the latter is active, unless agreed otherwise. The DA thus creates the basis for the data holder and the third-party data recipients to agree not to compete.

Pursuant to Recital 15, the scope of data the rights stipulated by Art.4-5 cover, is raw unprocessed data, directly generated by the user. Derived data and inferred data are thus not encompassed by the DA, and as shall be studied later, sector-specific regulations, e.g., DMA, go beyond in requiring also access to derived or inferred data, in addition to raw.

On the other hand, Art.3 appears to be addressing the question of how manufacturers or data holders gain legal control over the data in the first place, in a rather unsatisfactory manner. The provision requires that prior to the conclusion of a contract for the purchase, rent or lease of a product or a related service, the user is provided with certain topics or points of information in order to make the latter aware of the collection and use of data conducted by the product or service purchased or used by the user. What is not satisfying in this sense is that Art.3 does not require the contract to include that the user give up or sell the right to be monitored, by only requiring that the same is informed. Indirectly identifying the original data holder (oftentimes, this is the manufacturer of the device or part that includes the sensor), it is also evident from Art.3 that the third-party data holder may be the purchaser of the product that includes the sensor monitoring the user or, when the product is purchased directly by the user, the purchaser of the contractual right to monitor the user through the sensor. The contract between the user and the data holder (i.e., manufacturer or a third party), may thus be identified as a data mining or monitoring

agreement, and the same can thus be traded, since the DA still does not clarify the question of whether the user entering the contract has a “right” that is licensable or tradeable to the original data holder in the first place. Calling for the legislator to identify the subject of contract between the monitoree and the monitor, not yet having addressed the issue of whether the user is licensing the right to collect user generated data, the DA seems to accept the notion that the collector of the data (i.e., the company with the actual technical possibility to exclude others from mining the sensor) is the rightful “owner” of the data. In other words, it should be recognised that the starting point for the rules in questions should be that the owner of the sensor should be granted the ability to collect the data, with others being given a right to access and transfer the data collected, as is provided by Art.4-5. This means that the data generated by users should as a default rule be in the control of the holder of the property right of the sensor and the user, which could also be one and the same person, thereby ensuring that the right of the user is on equal footing as that of the data holder. This should have been envisioned in Art.3-5, and Art.11, which impose restrictions to the right of the user to utilise the data and guarantee the data holder the possibility to contractually restrict the user and the possibility to make use of technical protection measures under Art.6 on the harmonization of certain aspects of copyright and related rights to prevent access to the sensor. [1] [14]

Applicability to the DATAMITE Context

The following table provides in-principal indicative provisions applicability within the Pilot contexts. Of course, even this may be subject to nuanced interpretation and shall be further discussed again with partners in separate online sessions at the beginning of 2026 and re-confirmed finally, also regarding post-project exploitation. D4.5 should be consulted when overviewing the below table, as the first version of the report has explored in detail the roles and obligations that the DA sets. In addition, the guidelines to be provided to the functional & non-functional requirements concerning the tools shall also avail some further tailored legal & ethics context.

DA Provisions	Pilot 1	Pilot 2	Pilot 3	Pilot 4	Pilot 5	Pilot 6
Obligations of Data Holders on IoT B2C/B2B Data Sharing	Yes	–	–	–	–	–
Obligations of Data Holders on	Yes	–	Yes	Yes	–	–

DA Provisions	Pilot 1	Pilot 2	Pilot 3	Pilot 4	Pilot 5	Pilot 6
Mandatory B2B Data Sharing						
Obligations of Data Holders on B2G Data Sharing	Yes	–	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Obligations of Data Providers on Switching between Data Processing Services	–	–	–	–	–	–
Obligations of Data Providers on Interoperability	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Table 1. DA Provisions Applicability to Pilots

3.2.2 Digital Markets Act (DMA)

Intended Scope of Application

The DMA [2] sets rules for “gatekeepers” to abide by, in order to prevent anti-competitive behaviour. Three criteria determine whether a company falls within the scope of the Act, to be weighed in cumulatively, while the company also must be providing a so-called “core platform service” *to be able to qualify as a “gatekeeper”*. Firstly, the size that impacts the internal market must be present, and this is presumably the case if the company achieves an annual turnover in the European Economic Area (hereinafter “EEA”) equal to or exceeding EUR 7.5 billion in the three preceding financial years, or where its average market capitalisation or equivalent fair market value amounted to at least EUR 75 billion in the most recent financial year, and it provides a core platform service in at least three Member States. Secondly, the control of an important gateway for business users towards final consumers, which is presumably the case if the company operates a core platform service with more than 45 million monthly active end users

established or located in the EU and more than 10,000 yearly active business users established in the EU in the most recent financial year. Thirdly, an (expected) established and durable strong position, which is presumed to be the case if the company fulfilled the other two criteria in each of the past three financial years. “*Core platform services*” may include: Online intermediation services (e.g., marketplaces, app stores and online intermediation services in other sectors, such as mobility, transport or energy); Online search engines; Social networking; Video-sharing platform services; Number-independent, interpersonal, electronic communication services; Operating systems; Cloud services; and Advertising services, including advertising networks, advertising exchanges, as well as any other advertising intermediation services, where the latter are related to one or more of the other core platform services mentioned above. Two more services were added to the list then, after negotiations with the Parliament and the Council, and these are virtual assistants and web browsers. On the other hand, even though certain services, i.e. cloud services, operating systems and advertising services connected to platforms are included in the DMA, the same could also possibly fall under the related services pursuant Art. 3 of the DA or otherwise fall inside the Data Act, or otherwise fall inside the DA (e.g., Chap. 6 with regard to cloud services). [14]

Simplified Analysis of Core Provisions

Art. 5-7 of the Act postulates the relevant prohibitions to abide by for the Gatekeepers. It is important to note that paragraphs two, nine and ten of Art. 6, when read in combination, may provide access and portability right for business users. However, unlike the DA, the DMA does not provide stand-alone access and portability right for the benefit of business users vis-à-vis gatekeepers. In fact, Art. 6 postulates obligations for gatekeepers that are to be enforced by the Commission. As claimed by Björn Lundqvist [14], the end user may bring the data from the gatekeeper to the business user, thereby eliminating the gatekeeper’s access to the same data, which further asserts that the use of the notion of portability should be interpreted in the sense that the gatekeeper may not be allowed to keep a copy of said data. Furthermore, pursuant to Art.5(2), the platform provider is de facto not allowed to use the data generated by the business user on the platform in competition with the business user. Stemming from the obligation in Art.6(2), and in comparison, to the ones set by Art. 9-10, reflects that there is a sort of preferential right to the data generated that the business users have, vis-à-vis the platform provider. In other words, this constitutes a bilateral preferential right to each data point, thereby potentially overriding the general database right of the gatekeeper.

Even though, pursuant to Art.6(2), the gatekeeper still retains the prerogative to make all data available for all users, yet, in parallel, given that Art. 6(10) is directly applicable for business users, the latter have been granted a data advantage vis-à-vis the platforms – as the combination of the two paragraphs lead to an implicit compulsory access obligation that may be interpreted to be a right granted to the business user. Björn Lundqvist [14] claims that the right to access can also be traded, or at least access should be given to third parties contracted by the business user, who are acting as processors of this data for the business user. It is still to be considered whether the preceding interpretation is an overriding or countervailing right that also prevents gatekeepers from using their intellectual property rights to preclude access. On the other hand, as inferred data should also be accessible, distinguishing the line between data that originates from the business users and data that originates from the business (model) of the platform can be a difficult endeavour.

Pursuant to Preamble 60, there is an indication that the model for data access imagined by the EC is that the gatekeeper makes a data-access API available to business users and that the former is not allowed to use contractual or other restrictions to prevent such access. As asked by Björn Lundqvist [14], the question of whether this is an overruling right to all intellectual property rights of the gatekeeper is to be considered, but also, if this gateway to access and portability of data is an actual effective revolutionary tool for pursuing interoperability, or if, eventually, due to lack of a global technical API standard, established intellectual property legal systems, and also the GDPR, are to de facto prevent data access and portability. Furthermore, even though pursuant to Recital 70, is not allowed, with the aim of undermining interoperability, to use “unjustified technical protection measures”, or to unlawfully claim a copyright on APIs, it is questionable to what extent the breadth of copyright may be restricted a provision in a recital. After all, a restriction of copyright in a regulation may be in violation of the right to property as enshrined in Art. 17 of the EU Fundamental Rights Charter, and notwithstanding Recital 70, gatekeepers may still attempt to prevent access to their platforms and data by claiming that it is protected by intellectual property rights. [2] Another major problem that remains is the lack of clarity as to which data is in fact encompassed by the access and transfer right that the DMA grants, as the latter only contains an obligation for gatekeepers to give access, and as already explained, data can originate from both the business users’ activities and the platform providers’ activities, particularly in cases of inferred data. *All in all, and with reference to the DA above, the DMA should be the preferred tool for business users to gain access not only to raw data, but also derived data, while, as already outlined above, an obstacle facing such users can be gatekeepers claiming sui generis*

database right to the relevant dataset. What is more, even though future case law interpretations may still postulate that Art. 6 of the DMA provides a right to access to users, the wording of the document is such that it does not clearly and unambiguously establish it. [14]

Applicability to the DATAMITE Context

Even though the obligations that the DMA imposes on gatekeepers are not applicable within the DATAMITE context, and thus to any of its Pilots, as it is up-to-date, Consortium partners may still refer to the above analysis from the standpoint of potential business users. D4.5 may also be referred to for the full list of obligations regarding gatekeepers.

3.2.3 Digital Services Act (DSA)

Intended Scope of Application

The DSA [3] prescribes a set of obligations for service providers transmitting or storing data on behalf of users, i.e., intermediary service providers, with the obligations varying and increasing depending on whether the intermediary service provider also constitutes a hosting service, an online platform, an online marketplace or a very large online platform, or a very large online search engine. Among the providers of hosting services, a distinction is made between “online platforms” and “very large online platforms”, each subject to different levels of due diligence obligations. Being tiered and cumulative in their nature, the obligations set out impose the most onerous obligations on very large online platforms and very large search engines, in that the same are obliged to comply with all rules postulated regarding the lower categories of intermediary service providers. All in all, 5 main tiers to which the DSA legal framework is addressed may be distinguished, namely: Intermediary Service Providers (Section 1 of Chap. III); Hosting Services, including Online Platforms (Section 2 of Chap. III); Online Platforms (Section 3 of Chap. III); Online Platforms that Allow Consumers to Conclude Distance Contracts with Traders (Online Marketplaces) (Section 4 of Chap. III). VLOPs and VLOSEs (Section 5 of Chap. III). These have already been elaborately explained in the previous version of the report, namely, D4.5, which may be consulted for further reference to recall the provisions. D4.6 builds upon D4.5 by elaborating on with a more detailed analysis concerning very large platforms that has been inspired by Routledge, “Data Sharing Regulation in Europe” [14].

The obligations on very large platforms set by the DSA require the former to provide data access to the government of the data collected by the former, as indeed, accessing data from platforms may be needed by the government and researchers. *Thus, the DSA provides a framework for providing government and vetted researchers access to data from very large online platforms,*

whilst also ensuring that all the requirements for access to data under that framework are proportionate and appropriately protect the rights and legitimate interests, including trade secrets and other confidential information, of the platform and any other parties concerned, including service recipients.

Simplified Analysis of Core Provisions

Pursuant to Art. 31, regulators can order access for their own monitoring and enforcement purposes, but also for use by third-party researchers. More precisely, pursuant to Recital 63, to facilitate supervision and research into emerging risks brought about by the distribution of advertising online, very large online platforms should ensure public access to repositories of advertisements displayed on their online interfaces, as stipulated by Art. 30. The said emerging risks regard, e.g., illegal advertisements, manipulative techniques, disinformation with potential to negatively impact on public health and security, civil discourse, political participation or equality. Repositories are thus expected to include the contents of the given advertisements and data related to the advertiser and delivery of the advertisement, particularly when targeted advertising is present. Furthermore, these entities are granted the right to enquire access to or reporting of specific data, thereby securing the appropriate supervision and compliance of very large online platforms with regard to the obligations provided by Art. 26 on systemic risk and laid down by the MSs or the EC. Pursuant to the reading of the text, these requirements may include, e.g.: “the data necessary to assess the risks of illegal content of disinformation and possible harms brought about by a platform’s systems; data on the accuracy; functioning and testing of algorithmic systems for content moderation; recommender systems or advertising systems; or data on processes and outputs of content moderation or of internal complaint-handling systems” [14] within the meaning of the Act.

The initial proposal by the Commission, had limited data access to academic (“vetted”) researchers only, subjecting it to various conditions such as university affiliation, independence from commercial interests and compliance with confidentiality and security requirements, but following the proposals of the Council and the Parliament, an independent right to access has been created for researchers, with the scope of the latter also including independent researchers, including also those working for or affiliated with non-profit organisations. It should be underlined that the Council wanted to go further and create an independent right of access for researchers. Also, the European Parliament wanted to broaden the group that may access data to also include independent researchers working for or affiliated with non-profit organisations. [14] The

researchers may only use the data for the purpose of research into “systemic risks” as defined by Art. 26 of the DSA. At the same time, platforms may still object to data access requests in cases where they do not have the data or where access would create “significant vulnerabilities” to security, or prevent “protection of confidential information, in particular trade secrets”.

All in all, the Act unequivocally recognises the importance of investigations by researchers on the evolution and severity of online systemic risks, especially for bridging information asymmetries and establishing resilient risk mitigation systems. [14]

Applicability to the DATAMITE Context

Even though the obligations that the DSA imposes are not directly applicable within the DATAMITE context, and thus to any of its Pilots, as it is up-to-date, Consortium partners may still refer to the above analysis from the standpoint of potential applicability. D4.5 may also be referred to for the full list of obligations. The only two instances where DSA provisions could potentially apply within the DATAMITE context post-project in future time, as Pilot frameworks develop, could concern the following: Pilot 5 PSNC/WODR – Obligations of Online Platforms Acting as Online Marketplaces + Additional Obligations of Online Platforms; as well as Pilot 6 CINECA – Additional Obligations on Online Platforms; and which have been elaborately listed in D4.5. The potential for this shall be discussed and explained to the responsible partners in separate online sessions following the submission of D4.6.

3.2.4 Open Data Directive (ODD)

Intended Scope of Application

The ODD [4] stipulates routes for accessing government data, with its specific focus being the creation of a level playing field when making PSI available as an input to a commercial activity, i.e., when PSI is used as components in new products and services. After all, if public-sector bodies (hereinafter “PSBs”) offer information products or services exclusively, chances are that they would not be able to provide services as innovatively and efficiently as a structure governed by competition, and this could lead to a negative effect on competition in the European market. [14] Therefore, the Open Data Directive is aimed at overcoming these barriers, which limit the re-use of PSI in EU Member States.

Publicly funded research data is also covered by the Directive, the latter mandating, through its Art. 10(1), EU MS to develop open access policies for such data, and which ensure harmonised rules on the reuse via the repositories.

Simplified Analysis of Core Provisions

Pursuant to Art. 3 of the ODD, by requiring public-sector data collectors must grant access to data, the ODD thus tries to eliminate barriers, which could include attempts by PSBs to charge significant prices, unfair competition between the public and the private sectors, as well as practical issues hindering re-use (e.g., the lack of information on available PSI). The ODD is also hindering the attitude of PSBs that are slow to realise the economic potential of PSI.

Yet, the right to access public-sector information concerns public-good data only, which is not restricted by intellectual property rights held by the third party or the public authority, or business confidentiality limitations, and under the GDPR, with regard to personal data. As this has been perceived as a clear limitation of the ODD, the DGA invites the public sector to grant the right to re-use personal data, confidential data and data protected by IP rights to a natural or legal person (the re-user) for commercial or non-commercial purposes, subject to the requirement that the re-use is conducted in a manner respecting the rights and interests of businesses with regard to the related non-personal data, as well as data subjects with regard to the associated personal data. In cases of denied access to data for reuse, and in accordance with Art. 5(6), the PSB is still expected to assist the potential re-user in seeking consent from the given individual to reuse their personal data or permission from the data holder, given that their rights or interests may be affected

Whilst the full list of obligations stemming from the ODD can be recalled by referring to the former version of this report – D4.5 – the next section proceeds with analysis on the DGA.

Applicability to the DATAMITE Context

As publicly funded research data is also covered by the Directive, the latter mandating through its Art. 10(1), on EU MS to develop open access policies for such data, and which ensure harmonised rules on the reuse via the repositories, the EC has developed the concept of open research and the requirements for good data management in relation to the Horizon Europe research and innovation programmes, having incorporated the principle of “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”, i.e., with opt-outs being allowed in cases of justification. As the objective to make data not only open but FAIR (i.e., findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) has become prominent, so has the creation of a Data Management Plan become an obligation. *This concept and ongoing trend leading to sustainability standards are entirely intertwined with the language of the ODD*, as well as with the subsequent “Recommendation on access to and preservation of scientific information” that have been issued in alignment with the ODD, and in order to prepare

the then forthcoming new Horizon Europe Research Framework Programme, thereby reflecting the ongoing developments at the EU level of the European Open Science Cloud, thus acknowledging the increased capacity of data analytics of today and its role in research.

The data management implementation within DATAMITE is extending the FAIR principles thus also to the datasets collected and generated in the innovation activities of the project, whenever possible, as many of the datasets are industrial data belonging to the industrial partners in the consortium. To safeguard the application of the principles, the DATAMITE project results are being stored on different repositories. DATAMITE uses Zenodo, (a service funded by the EC, which is supported and maintained by CERN and integrated in the European Open Science Cloud), GitHub for code, as well as the DATAMITE website for project open access documentation. The Zenodo repository service is aligned to the FAIR principles. Regarding storage of datasets, the project has selected Zenodo as a distributed data repository storage for open access uploads, since the latter facilitates the respect for the open-source best practices, such as the transparency, the openness, as well as the vendor-neutral open collaboration.

Furthermore, being associated with significant socioeconomic benefits, high-value datasets that have been given special attention by the ODD, are also of relevance to the DATAMITE context. Selected from within six thematic categories, and outlined in Annex I of the Directive, the same cover: *geospatial; earth observation and environment; meteorological; statistics; companies and company ownership; mobility*. With due regard to the datasets that partners have confirmed before LIF, *this means that the datasets that Pilots 1, 4, 5 and 6 are responsible for, certainly fall within this category*. As postulated by Art. 5(8), the reuse in this regard must be ensured by making the datasets available free of charge, in machine-readable formats, as well as via Application Programming Interfaces (hereinafter “APIs”) and bulk download.

Finally, it should be noted that stemming from Art. 5(5), businesses, particularly startups, are allowed the freedom to innovate products/services, through being offered access to more real-time (dynamic) (changing asynchronously over time as new information becomes available) data. This data must be made available by public sector bodies for reuse immediately upon collection via APIs, as a bulk download, where relevant. [4]

3.2.5 Data Governance Act (DGA)

Intended Scope of Application

The DGA [3] is focused on the governance of data sharing across sectors, including public sector data. It also establishes a framework for data intermediation services to operate in a trustworthy

manner, as well as promotes data altruism, thereby aiming at increasing the availability of data by voluntarily donating data.

Simplified Analysis of Core Provisions

3.2.5.1 Access to Data

Art. 5 of the DGA stipulates that public-sector bodies that are competent under national law to grant or refuse access for the re-use of data that covered by commercial confidentiality, statistical confidentiality, protection of intellectual property rights of third parties, or protection of personal data, are to make the conditions for allowing re-use of such data publicly available. These conditions are to be non-discriminatory, proportionate and objectively justified with regard to categories of data, purposes of re-use and the nature of the data for which re-use is allowed, and the same are not be used to restrict competition. Art. 5 further stipulates that PSBs can set an obligation on the re-user to anonymise or pseudonymise personal data, or delete commercially confidential information, including trade secrets, before the data may be re-used. In addition, PSB are expected to be able to verify any results of the re-user's processing of data, with the former reserving the right to prohibit the use of results that contain information jeopardising the rights and interests of third parties. PSBs are thus also expected to ensure that any confidential information is not disclosed as a result of the re-use. As a rule, the re-use under the DGA, is allowed only in compliance with intellectual property rights and the GDPR; and if efforts by the PSB to comply, e.g., through anonymisation of personal data are not unambiguously successful, the re-use of data cannot be granted. Yet, re-users shall be supported by the PSB in seeking consent from the data subjects and/or permission from the legal entities whose rights and interests may be affected by the re-use – of course, where this should be feasible and would not incur disproportionate cost for the PSB. [3]

3.2.5.2 Data-Sharing Service

Aiming to counter the dominance of large tech companies, the DGA promotes voluntary data sharing by facilitating data exchange through intermediation services. Acting as neutral third parties, the latter connect SMEs and start-ups with data users, charging for facilitating data sharing without using the data for direct financial gain. Both standalone and additional service providers can serve intermediaries, subject to strict separation. The conditions that must be met by data-sharing services could be summarised as follows. [3]:

- The provider is not allowed to use the data for which it provides services for purposes other than to put them at the disposal of data users, with the data-sharing services having to be placed in a separate legal entity.
- The metadata collected from the provision of the data-sharing service could only be used for the development of that service.
- The provider has the responsibility to ensure that the procedure for access to its service is fair, transparent and non-discriminatory for both data holders and data users, including with regard to prices.
- The exchange of the data in the format received from the data holder should be facilitated by the provider, with the latter being allowed to convert the data into specific formats only when enhancing interoperability within and across sectors is required, or if requested by the data user, or where mandated by Union law, or to ensure harmonisation with international or European data standards.
- Procedures shall be in place to prevent fraudulent or abusive practices in relation to access to data from parties seeking access through the services of the provider.
- The provider shall secure a reasonable continuity of provision of its services and, when services which ensure storage of data are provided, the former shall ensure that sufficient guarantees are in place, allowing data holders and data users to obtain access to their data in case of insolvency.
- Adequate technical, legal and organisational measures shall be put in place by the provider, for the prevention of transfer or access to non-personal data that is unlawful under Union law.
- Measures to ensure a high level of security for the storage and transmission of non-personal data shall be ensured by the provider through particular measures.
- Procedures shall be put in place by the prover to ensure compliance with the Union and national rules on competition.

3.2.5.3 Data Altruism Organisations

Data altruism concerns the common good as it increases data availability through voluntarily data donation by recognised non-profit entities. Topics of concern and aimed objectives may relate to, e.g., healthcare, improving mobility, improving the provision of public services, etc. Entities making available relevant data for altruistic purposes are to register as “data altruism organisation recognised in the Union”, by also complying with transparency requirements, safeguards for data

donors, as well as the forthcoming Rulebook which shall lay down certain requirements, the latter being outlined by Art. 22. Moreover, as per Art. 19, only recognised data altruism organisations who have chosen to register with the respective authority are subject to the DGA provisions. To complete such a registration, an application to the competent authority containing information related to, e.g., legal status, registration number, etc., shall be submitted. D4.5 may be referred to for the detailed list of obligations concerning such organisations. [3]

Applicability to the DATAMITE Context

Firstly, it is possible that public-sector data provisions within the meaning of the DGA could apply to some of the DATAMITE Pilots, especially to Pilot 3 and Pilot 4. Even though it is true that “open data” is oftentimes fully accessible under open licenses, not all “electricity distribution” data may be truly “open” in a manner that excludes the need for protection. In these cases, offering data to service providers using DataSpaces, or leveraging electricity distribution open data – if certain (DSO/TSO) data originates from public-sector bodies, particularly data protected, as public utility data usually is (e.g., grid load, usage), which may contain trade secrets of commercially confidential information, and thus trigger the application of Art. 3 DGA. More specifically, this could be, e.g., grid data involving non-public or infrastructure-specific data, but also personal consumption, maybe particularly sensitive. Also, if any of the datasets utilised by Pilot 5 (using data from public institutions, e.g., environmental monitoring, agricultural services, meteorological networks) are not fully open, then the DGA could still apply.

Secondly, within the context of the DATAMITE Project, as it is up-to-date, there are no data intermediary parties in the strict legal sense, as is provided under the DGA. Even though certain DATAMITE components function as a technical de-facto intermediary (e.g., data-space connectors and sharing modules). Therefore, the DGA provisions could potentially apply in the future only given that there is an actual post-project commercialisation, offering to third parties as neutral services, operating without data repurposing, and of course, subject to the mandatory official notification under Art. 11 of the DGA. For instance, the highest likelihood for the intermediary provisions to eventually apply concerns Pilots 3, especially, but also Pilot 4 and Pilot 5.

Finally, up-to-date, there are no altruistic organisations within the DATAMITE Pilots. Should this change in the future, then the related altruism provisions would become applicable. For example, there is a high potential for data altruism rules to apply in the future to Pilot 6 if data is donated altruistically (for research purposes).

All of the above shall be further evaluated and reconfirmed during the online Pilot sessions that LIF shall organise shortly after the submission of D4.6.

3.2.6 Free Flow of Non-Personal Data Directive (FFD)

Intended Scope of Application

The FFD [6] is a governing framework for the administration of datasets consisting of non-personal data or mixed ones, to the part of the dataset constituting non-personal data, and without prejudice to the GDPR. The FFD has addressed vendor lock-in practices, which the DA has further addressed. It also lays down obligations for MSs by generally prohibiting them from setting out data localisation requirements.

Simplified Analysis of Core Provisions

As already explained above in Section 3.1.4 discussing the nature of non-personal data, it should be recalled that, both the GDPR and the FFD, could potentially apply to mixed datasets containing both personal and non-personal data. However, as per Art. 2 of the GDPR [7], whenever personal and non-personal data are inseparably linked in a dataset, and may not be distinguished or separated, the GDPR takes precedence over the FFD, thus applying to the entire mixed dataset, even if personal data is a small or secondary fraction thereof. The concept of “inextricably linked” is not explicitly defined from a regulatory point of view, but the EC has suggested in its Guidance on the FFD, that it refers to instances where separating personal and non-personal data would be practically impossible, economically inefficient or technically unfeasible for the data controller. Therefore, it is the data controller who is largely entrusted with the power to decide on whether data are “inseparable”, thereby weighing the costs of distinguishing the data against the potential reduction in the value of resulting datasets. As respondent companies from different sectors have largely reported that separating data was likely to be costly or very costly, and as non-personal data are defined in contrast to personal data, leading to uncertainty among business stakeholders as to what exactly is the boundary between the two, the interpretation of personal data by case law has led to further complications by making it challenging to exclude the application of the GDPR or identify rules for specific situations. Consequently, limiting the cases where FFD may apply, the GDPR makes non-personal data rare. [14]

As recognised by the EC, mixed datasets are generally subject to the GDPR, which entails fulfilling all obligations of data controllers and processors, as well as ensuring the rights of data subjects, regarding any data-sharing operation involving mixed databases. This means that *both the sharing and receiving companies must ensure robust security levels for the entire dataset,*

pursuant to the provisions of Art. 5(f) of the GDPR. [7] There is still the alternative of personal data anonymisation, but this, too, requires the distinction of data and entails a cost for the data holder. Moreover, *the risk of liability in cases of incorrect anonymisation should be considered*, too. [14]

Another important aspect of the FFD is the prohibition concerning MSs to set out data localisation requirements, unless required by national security, as pointed defined by Art. 4(1), which means that organisations cannot be forced to store or process data within their borders. “Data localisation requirement” refers to any obligation, prohibition, condition, limit or other requirement, which mandates data processing in the territory of a specific MS or hinders the processing of data in any other MS. However, MSs’ right to request or obtain access to the data for performance of their official duties has been preserved under Art. 5 In addition, stemming from the overall logic of the FFD, and as referred to by Preamble 13, it is crucially important that companies themselves also refrain from imposing data localisation restrictions when using data processing services. [6]

Applicability to the DATAMITE Context

The FFD lays down rules for “data processing services in the broadest sense”, comprising services such as Infrastructure-as-a-Service (for data storage), Platform-as-a-Service, and Software-as-a-Service. Even though the FFD does not directly address open-source and multi-domain software by allowing the free flow of non-personal data, one may draw a conclusion that the same can support the availability and accessibility of data that can be used by open-source software projects or multi-domain software applications. The Document also indirectly addresses the interaction with databases and systems by encouraging the free flow of non-personal data, by aiming at removing unnecessary restrictions on where data is stored and processed, thereby ensuring that businesses and organisations can freely transfer non-personal data between different MSs within the EU

FFD Provisions	Pilot 1	Pilot 2	Pilot 3	Pilot 4	Pilot 5	Pilot 6
Obligations on the Handling of Mixed Datasets	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	–	–

FFD Provisions	Pilot 1	Pilot 2	Pilot 3	Pilot 4	Pilot 5	Pilot 6
Obligations on the Porting of Non-Personal Data	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Table 2. FFD Provisions Applicability to Pilots

3.3 Sectoral Regulations

3.3.1 Data Spaces

Aimed at enacting data-access regimes on a sector-specific level, the creation of Data Spaces has been envisioned and is ongoingly supported by the European Commission through investments and sector-specific regulations. Under a data space, both public and private entities should be encouraged and obliged to provide their data to the data spaces, so that anyone who may need and want access to develop new products and services, irrespective of whether the given comer is a private or public entity, is granted the possibility to do so. As per the EC, the following areas are prone to hold common data spaces: Agriculture; Cultural Heritage; Energy; Finance; Green Deal; Health; Language; Manufacturing; Media; Mobility; Public Administration; Research and Innovation; Skills; Tourism. [20] In addition to sector-specific legal systems mandating data sharing in specific industries, there may be similar rules, such as codes of conduct, which constitute a so-called “Best Practices” setting good examples to be followed. Of course, many more are yet to be further developed and new ones to be enacted. The most relevant to the DATAMITE context in this regard pieces of legislation and soft law instruments for the facilitation of effective data sharing abiding by best standards are thus referred to below.

3.3.1.1 Regulation on the Internal Market for Electricity & Directive on Common Rules for the Internal Market for Electricity

The Common European Energy Data Space, the *Regulation on the Internal Market for Electricity* [21] and the *Directive on Common Rules for the Internal Market for Electricity* [22], as well as the *Regulation on Interoperability Requirements and Non-Discriminatory and Transparent Procedures for Access to Metering and Consumption Data* [23] (the latter being discussed in the next section) are crucial in their aim at creating a competitive, consumer-focused, and sustainable electricity market. The regulatory documents emphasise the importance of integration of renewable energy, efficient cross-border electricity trade, and improving system efficiency. They

also highlight the importance of data sharing and interoperability in the Energy sector, supporting the development and use of Data Spaces to facilitate the exchange of data across different systems and service providers. Both the Energy Data Space, with its goals and challenges, as well as the respective pieces of legislation have already been discussed in D4.5, but the analysis is herewith being further developed (particularly regarding the Regulation on Interoperability), based also on the on-site workshop conducted by LIF during the Plenary Meeting in Aachen.

Prior to developing further the next section on the Regulation on Interoperability, we shall recall the requirements set by the *Regulation on the Internal Market for Electricity* and the *Directive on Common Rules for the Internal Market for Electricity*, with all three being applicable to the nature of work related to the Pilot 3 and Pilot 4 contexts.

- Art. 23 of the Directive mandates access to customer data via data hubs or comparable solutions in a non-discriminatory and transparent manner, emphasising the need for consumer consent and data protection. This is critical for both Pilot 3 and Pilot 4 to ensure that the use of energy data complies with consumer consent requirements, thereby promoting trust. [22]
- Art. 24 of the Regulation stipulates the obligation to provide interoperability of data exchange formats and protocols across MSs, therefore supporting Pilot 4's focus on integrating diverse data sources while ensuring interoperability across platforms. [21]
- Art. 34 of the Regulation further supports the development of transparent, non-discriminatory mechanisms to access metering and consumption data, ensuring fair market participation. [21]
- According to Art. 55(1)(d) and (e) of the Regulation, DSOs are required to contribute to the digitalisation of distribution systems, including the deployment of smart grids and intelligent metering systems and support the development of data management, cyber security and data protection. [21]

3.3.1.2 Regulation on Interoperability Requirements and Non-Discriminatory and Transparent Procedures for Access to Metering and Consumption Data

Regulation (EU) 2023/1162 [23] supports Pilot 3 and Pilot 4 further by ensuring through Art. 1(1), interoperability, legal compliance, and transparency in data exchange procedures related to electricity metering and consumption data by final customers and eligible parties. The Regulation provides a framework for secure data sharing, promoting standardised procedures for data access, but it further emphasises consumer rights and data protection. Art. 11 of the Regulation

outlines the cooperation on data transparency between the EU DSO entity and ENTSO for Electricity to ensure transparent and non-discriminatory access to data across the EU.

During the dedicated workshop session in Aachen, Pilots 3-4, but also Pilot 1 who has confirmed that on certain instances outside the context of the Project, they handle such data, and thus attended, too – have been duly advised on how to identify and distinguish between the key parties acting in national markets that the Regulation has envisaged, following which the same have confirmed to verify with their organisations certain metrics and aspects of interpretation regarding the respective roles. An interactive exercise in that regard has been organised by Lif in Aachen. As explained, the designated roles are as follows. [23]

- Pursuant to Art. 2(7), a “Metered Data Administrator” means a party responsible for storing validated historical metering and consumption data and distributing these data to final customers and/or eligible parties.
- Pursuant to Art. 2(12), a “Metering Point Administrator”: means a party responsible for administering and making available the characteristics of a metering point, including the registrations of eligible parties and final customers linked to the metering point.
- Pursuant to Art. 2(13), a “Data Access Provider” means a party responsible for facilitating access, including in cooperation with other parties, to validated historical metering and consumption data by the final customer or by eligible parties.
- Pursuant to Art. 2(10), a “Permission Administrator” means a party responsible for administering a register of data access permissions for a set of metering points, making this information available to final customers and eligible parties in the sector, on request.

The obligations associated with the roles are then enshrined in Art. 5-8. [23]

- *Art. 5 on the “Metered Data Administrator” Obligations.* To ensure access to data for final customers and eligible parties, this party shall: Make validated metering and consumption data available to final customers and eligible parties [...] through an online or through another appropriate interface, on request, in a non-discriminatory way, and without undue delay; Ensure that final customers (i) can access their validated metering and consumption data; (ii) can make it available to eligible parties and (iii) receive it in a structured, commonly used, machine-readable and interoperable format; Keep a data access log up to date and make this available to final customers through an online or through another appropriate interface, free of charge, without unnecessary delay, and on final customer’s request; When transferring data to eligible parties, and respecting relevant personal data

protection law, ensure, in cooperation with the permission administrator where applicable, that there is an active permission or another legal basis for the data to be lawfully transmitted or processed [...]. Metered Data Administrators shall also keep complementary information on historical metering and consumption data [...]. For the duration of the retention period, the same shall be kept available, along with the corresponding log information, for access by final customers and eligible parties on final customers' request. The party is also expected to give eligible parties access to testing facilities where the latter can test the compatibility of their systems with the systems of the metered data administrator implementing the procedures in this Regulation. The testing facility shall be available before the procedures are implemented and while they are in operation.

- *Art. 6 on the “Metering Point Administrator” Obligations.* Shall inform the permission administrator, and where relevant at national level the metered data administrator, without undue delay, of any changes in the assignment of final customers to metering points, and of any other external occurrences that invalidate active permissions granted in their area of responsibility.
- *Art. 7 on the “Data Access Provider” Obligations.* Shall make publicly available through an online interface: All relevant procedures they use for providing access to data as described by the reference model set out in this Chapter and the Annex where the specific case of access by final customers is presented; as well as the means for final customers to access, without unnecessary delay, their historical metering and consumption data, in cooperation with the metered data administrator where applicable [...]. This party shall keep and make available to final customers their log information, including the time at which an eligible party or a final customer has been given access to data, and the type of data concerned. This information shall be made available online, free of charge, without unnecessary delay, whenever a final customer requests access.
- *Art. 8 on the “Permission Administrator” Obligations.* Shall: Grant permission to access validated historical metering and consumption data to eligible parties and revoke permissions, without unnecessary delay, on final customers' request [...]; Provide final customers on request, with an overview of active and historical data sharing permissions [...]; Process notifications about invalidations of permissions received in line with the procedures in this Regulation; Inform the metered data administrator [...], the eligible party if needed [...] and the final customer [...] as soon as the permission administrator is notified of an invalidation of a permission; Keep a permission provision log for the final

customers and make this information available to them online, free of charge, without undue delay, and on their request; Make publicly available the relevant procedures they use for providing access to data [...]. Permission Administrators shall cooperate with eligible parties and meter data administrators to facilitate testing of the processes to implement the reference model. This cooperation is to take place before the processes are implemented and while they are in operation.

3.3.1.3 EU Codes of Conduct

3.3.1.3.1 Code of Conduct on Data Centre Energy Efficiency

Albeit not directly applicable to the data sharing process per se, as well as not imposing direct obligations on the Consortium partners within the Project context, in view of the Project overall sustainability “lead by example” goals reflecting the EU’s commitment to reducing energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions, and following the best practices approach, the existence of the *Best Practice document for the European Code of Conduct for Energy Efficiency in Data Centres* [24] should be acknowledged and consulted further.

The language of the code is directly intertwined with the targets of the European Union’s Energy Efficiency Directive, which although targeting predominantly larger facilities, provides valuable lessons also for smaller data centres and server room operations with capabilities below 500kW.

Abiding by the principles is not just a response to regulatory trends; it is an investment in resilience, sustainability, and long-term success. The said provisions are a catalyst for change in the data centre industry, and while its direct mandates may not currently apply to smaller facilities, the principles promoted are universally beneficial. By embracing energy audits, optimising cooling and server efficiency, leveraging renewable energy, and fostering a culture of sustainability, smaller data centres can reduce costs, enhance competitiveness, and prepare for a greener future. Proactively abiding by the highest sustainability standards may thus be achieved also indirectly by any organisation, whenever considering data centre and server room choices.

3.3.1.3.2 Code of Conduct on Agricultural Data Sharing by Contractual Agreement

Aimed at helping farmers make well-informed decisions that improve the quality and quantity of their production, with less labour and less impact on the environment, the future effectiveness of farmer technologies may only be ensured upon the willingness of farmers to share their data with agribusinesses that develop digital technologies. With the intention to foster trust in that regard, the *EU Code of Conduct for agricultural data sharing by contractual agreement* was launched in 2018 which encourages transparency about data use, has been released, with the same being

applicable within the nature of work related to Pilot 5. [25] The scope of the Code covers different types of agricultural data (non-exhaustive list) in the agro-food sector, e.g.: farm data (agronomic data, compliance data regarding control and enforcement relation to competent authorities, livestock data), machine data, service data (e.g., data used for vehicle maintenance and repair), agri-supply data (input) (related to the nature, composition and use of inputs such as fertilisers, feedstuffs, plant protection products, etc.), agri-service provider data (originating from an agricultural services provider operating to benefit a client (e.g., farmers). Personal data, as per the GDPR provisions, is also covered.

Whilst some of the most core trust in farm data sharing principles are outlined in the table below [26], the subsequent paragraph lists the main legal principles establishing a balanced contract [25] – *the content constituting a direct copy from the original sources.*

Principles	Key Features
Data Ownership	<p>“Rights are assigned to the entity that engages in the creation/collection of agri-data either independently, via advanced machinery or by way of commissioning data providers to do so (i.e., Data originator)</p> <p>This entitles the ‘data originator’ to exclusive control over agri-data, its subsequent use, access and/or distribution</p> <p>‘Data originators’ can be farmers, but also other parties in the value-chain whose data are being collected (such as, for example, input suppliers, nurseries, the slaughterhouse)”</p>
Data Access/Control/Portability	<p>“The access, use, storage and potential sharing of ag data with third parties is <i>only</i> permitted if the ‘data originator’ explicitly consents to this in the contract”</p>
Data Protection and Transparency	<p>“Unauthorised agri-data sharing cannot occur with third parties that are not originally referred to in the contract</p> <p>Prior consent must first be received to rectify the contract should circumstances change, and include the intended third parties</p> <p>Personal, or sensitive information requires replacement with pseudonyms (artificial identifiers) to ensure it is ‘less identifiable”</p>

Principles	Key Features
Privacy and Security	<p>“Personal data should not be subject to potential losses, theft, or unauthorised access</p> <p>the need to notify ‘data originators’ of any security breaches that may occur</p> <p>GDPR becomes applicable in circumstances where a data originator’s personal/sensitive data is exploited to the advantage of third parties and utilised to ‘make decisions about the data originator as a natural person”</p>
Liability and Intellectual Property Rights	<p>“The contractual agreements must entail any terms of liability</p> <p>However, liability does not ensue from the faultiness of data machinery or devices during farming operations. There must be protection of any relevant IP rights that may result from the agri-data value chain”</p>

Table 3. Trust in Farm Data Sharing: Reflections on the EU Code of Conduct for Agricultural Data Sharing[26]

Whenever using a product or service that captures or uses agricultural data, the following questions shall be answered [25]:

- *“Is there an agreement/contract in place?*
- *What obligations are there? What warranties and indemnities are there for each party?*
- *What data is collected?*
- *Who owns/controls access to the data?*
- *What services are delivered?*
- *Will my data be used for purposes other than providing me, the data originator (e.g. farmer), a service? Is it clear what these are? Can I agree/disagree?*
- *What are/is the benefits/value for me (as data originator)?*
- *Is the data shared with other parties? What rules do the external parties adhere to? Can I agree/disagree with sharing data with other parties?*
- *Can the service provider change the agreements unilaterally?*

- *What happens when the service provider changes ownership?*
- *Can I retrieve my dataset from the system in a usable format?*
- *Will I be updated on security breaches?*
- *Can I opt out of the service and have my data deleted from the system?*
- *Is there a contact point to assist me with any questions that I may have?*
- *Do I need insurance?*
- *What are the confidentiality terms?"*

As evident from the language/intent of the Code, a contract can certainly contribute significantly towards establishing trust relationships, thereby mitigating the detrimental effects of power relationships between experts and non-experts. Yet, and as argued by Simone van der Burg, as well as Leanne Wiseman and Jovana Krkeljas [26], such contract may only be successful in fostering trust when 1. information is comprehended by the more vulnerable party in the given relationship who must sign the contract, 2. the partner in the more powerful position takes responsibility to provide that information, as well as 3. Whenever data is reused over a longer period, the information is tailored to the information needs of the party signing the contract accordingly.

3.4 Wrap-Up of the Data Sharing Legal Framework

Inspired by the comparative approach taken by Laura Zoboli and Maciej Bernatt [14], a brief overview of the core data-sharing regulatory framework is provided in the table below.

Regulation	Data Type	Pro-Sharing Objective	Main Tools
DA	Private Data	Private Date Sharing	Obligations to share data (B2C, B2B, B2G) + general framework for data access and sharing
ODD/DGA	Public Data	Public Data Reuse ("as open as possible")	Obligation on Public Sector Bodies to offer public data for reuse (G2B)

Regulation	Data Type	Pro-Sharing Objective	Main Tools
DMA	Private Data	Private Data Access and Portability	Obligation on gatekeepers to provide access and portability rights
GDPR	Personal Data	Free Flow and Data Protection	Framework for digital trust + portability + transfer, etc.
FFD	Non-Personal Data	Free Flow	Ban on data localisation measures
Other	Various	Sector-Specific	Sector-specific legislation and sectoral data spaces

Table 4. Coherence of EU Data Sharing Acquis

4 Personal Data Protection and Its Role in Defining the Legal Framework

Chapter 4 is an in-depth, structured analysis of the personal data protection implications concerning any data storage and data sharing processes. All applicable points have been verified and ensured with the Consortium, and the same are further addressed in the constituent functional & non-functional requirements list, which is being shared shortly after the submission of D4.6.

4.1 Key Data Protection Principles

Identifying the *GDPR [7] material and territorial scope of application* is a step to consider first. As defined by its Recital 26, for the GDPR to apply, information must relate to an identified or identifiable natural person, meaning that it must be possible to identify a person directly or indirectly by means of an identifier, e.g., names, identification numbers, location data, or a specific physical factor, etc. Therefore, pseudonymised data are still considered personal data, since the identifiers have not been irrevocably removed. Only data that has been anonymised, that does not constitute (reasonable) risk of re-identification, remains outside the scope of the GDPR. Furthermore, as a far-reaching regulation, the GDPR applies to any organisation that processes personal data of individuals within the European Union and the European Economic Area, irrespective of where that organisation is located. Secondly, with its core emphasis being the protection of personal data, the GDPR provisions mandate that organisations constantly abide by the key principles established therein, and which are outlined below. All internal policies and actions within an organisation are to be developed and maintained in compliance with the same. Furthermore, clarifying *the notion of processing* is another essential element to study, prior to proceeding with the key principles. The broad definition that the GDPR gives to the notion of personal data processing, i.e., as covering everything one does with personal data, is evident in Art. 4(2) of the Regulation which refers to processing as “[a]ny operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction.” Finally, *the notions of controller and processor* are used to delineate and assign the tasks, responsibilities and liability

of entities processing personal data. Whilst in accordance with Art. 4, the controller is the entity deciding, or jointly together with another controller, on the purpose and the means of the processing, the processor is the entity processing the data on behalf of the controller.

Art. 5 GDPR then lays down the basic tenets allowing for *lawful processing of personal data*, with the same being summarised below.

- *Lawfulness, Fairness, and Transparency*: To be lawful, the processing of personal data must be based on one of the six legal bases defined by Art. 6 GDPR, and which are discussed below. The principles of fairness and transparency, then, refers to the obligation to inform data subjects in a comprehensive manner about the purpose and scope of the processing, as postulated by Art. 12-14 GDPR.
- *Purpose Limitation*: Pursuant to the principle of transparency, data can only be processed for a specific purpose, and which must be communicated to the data subject. As shall be observed in the subsequent pages, Art. 89 GDPR allows for certain derogations in the context of research, given that the requirements under that article are fulfilled, allowing for further processing.
- *Data Minimisation*: Only the minimum data needed for the purposes of the organisation should be considered by the controller, i.e., the minimum amount of data required to meet the needs for executing the given task must then be the maximum amount of data held by data processors. In addition, data must be adequate, relevant, and limited. Therefore, it is not acceptable to collect data on the basis that it may be of use at a later period.
- *Accuracy*: The controller has an obligation to ensure the accuracy of the data. This means that giving data subject the right to have inaccurate data corrected must be ensured, too.
- *Storage Limitation*: Organisations are prohibited from keeping personal data for longer than necessary regarding the purposes of the initial processing, with only exception applying in cases of public interest, scientific or historical research, statistics, etc., as provided by Art. 89 GDPR, and given that the requirements related thereto are fulfilled. This exception is analysed in the forthcoming section. As a rule, the Storage Limitation principle thus requires controllers to specify the time limit after which data is deleted.
- *Integrity and Confidentiality*: Oftentimes referred to as the “Security principle”, this one obliges organisations to put in place appropriate technical and organisational measures for the protection of personal data from unauthorised or unlawful processing, destruction, damage. In other words, this is necessitated to avoid the risk of encountering data leaks

or breaches. Organisations must take security measures to ensure that data being processed is anonymised, encrypted, or at the very least pseudonymised, thereby making potential serious data breaches less likely. The principle extends beyond cybersecurity and thus includes both physical and organisational security, thereby protecting data on paper, too. In addition, pursuant to Art. 33-34 GDPR, national data protection authorities and/or data subjects, given that the breach is likely to cause a high risk to the rights and freedoms of the latter, must be notified concerning any leaks or breaches. The notification obligation must be executed with undue delay, and not later than 72 hours from the moment of becoming aware of the data breach.

- **Accountability:** Accountability sets the obligation on organisations to be able to demonstrate that they are compliant with all the above six principles. This means that if GDPR compliance may not be proven through measures and records in place, thereby allowing for compliance to be demonstrated across special categories, then technically, no compliance exists.

In addition, pursuant to Art. 6(1) GDPR, processing is *lawful only if at least one of the following applies*.

- **Consent:** As postulated by Art. 4, consent must be given freely by the user/data subject; it must be specific and particular, and not combined with other topics; the consent given must constitute an informed decision in that it is based on an easy-to-read explanation regarding the data being collected, the reasons for the collection, and the manner in which the same is being used. The rationale is closely linked to the principle of fairness and lawfulness. Moreover, the consent granted must constitute an unambiguous indication, e.g., selection of a checkbox or an “Agree” button, or a signed document, thereby making it clear that the data subject consents to a particular processing activity.
- **Contractual Performance:** This basis is applicable in cases when the processing is required to perform contractual obligations, including the data subject.
- **Legitimate Interest:** This legal basis applies when processing the data is necessary for one’s legitimate interests, unless the latter overrides the rights and freedoms of the data subjects. Legitimate interest in this context refers to any interest providing a benefit to one or more parties involved in the processing, and the same can be personal, commercial, or even societal. For example, processing data in the interest of one’s business, the GDPR legitimate interest provision may be applicable, given that the interest may violate the fundamental rights and freedoms of data subjects.

- *Vital Interest*: Life-related scenarios and the protection of vital interests of data subjects are concerned.
- *Legal Requirement*: This basis is applicable whenever processing is necessary to fulfil a legal obligation.
- *Public Interest*: Whenever processing data is necessary for the performance of a task in the general public's interest, the public interest basis applies, and the same is usually applicable to public or private entities performing tasks in the public interest.

Moreover, whenever *sensitive data* are processed, Art. 9(2)(a) GDPR mandates the collection of *explicit consent* from the data subject, i.e., involving a stronger affirmative action by the data subject. The term “explicit” refers to the manner in which the data subject expresses his or her consent, meaning that the latter must be given in an unequivocally expressive way. An obvious way “[...] to make sure consent is explicit [...] would be to expressly confirm consent in a written statement. Following the *Article 29 WP, Guidelines on consent under Regulation 2016/679*, where appropriate, the controller could make sure the written statement is signed by the data subject, in order to remove all possible doubt and potential lack of evidence in the future.” The controller can also rely on other means, e.g., a two-step verification or the “data subject may be able to issue the required statement by filling in an electronic form, by sending an email, by uploading a scanned document carrying the signature of the data subject, or by using an electronic signature”.

The “Research Exemption”

Acknowledging the need for facilitation of different types of research, Art. 89 GDPR refers to scientific, historical, statistical research, as well as archiving in the public interest. With no formal definition of what constitutes *scientific research*, applying a wide approach, Recital 159 GDPR states that “the processing of personal data for scientific research purposes should be *interpreted in a broad manner, including for example, technological development and demonstration, fundamental research, applied research and privately funded research.*” Recital 33 GDPR adds to this by stating that:

“[...] it is often not possible to fully identify the purpose of personal data processing for scientific research purposes at the time of data collection. Therefore, data subjects should be allowed to give their consent to certain areas of scientific research when in keeping with recognised ethical standards for scientific research. Data subjects should have the opportunity to give their consent *only to certain areas* of research or parts of research projects *to the extent allowed by the intended purpose.*”

Applying a rather wide scope of notion concerning research, abiding by the proportionality principle, Art. 89 GDPR yet sets a baseline in requiring that any research derogation is subject to

the existence of *appropriate safeguards* for the rights and freedoms of data subjects, e.g.: data minimisation; technical and organisational measures; privacy by design and by default; pseudonymisation (if anonymisation is not possible) unless this would also prejudice the purpose of the research. In addition, respect for adequate ethical standards, including the requirements for obtaining *ethical approvals*, is part of these safeguards [27]. In other words, being inextricably linked to the research exemption, any research project must meet the established quality standards and processes required for conducting research. If the said safeguards are met, derogations to the following points may then be applied: further processing and storage limitation (Art. 5(1)(b) and (e) GDPR); processing of special categories of data (Art. 9(2)(j) GDPR); information provided by third parties (Art. 14(5)(b) GDPR); right to erasure (Art. 17(3)(d) GDPR); right to object (Art. 21(6) GDPR). In case of any derogation being applied to the listed provisions, the *principles of proportionality and necessity* are to be taken into account, with the assessment to be conducted prior to the application of the derogations, and subject to *diligent documentation*. Furthermore, derogations regarding the following points may be allowed by EU or Member State law: the right to access; the right to rectification; the right to restrict processing; the right to object. To be allowed to rely on any of these derogations, the safeguards outlined above are again to be applied. In addition, pursuant to the necessity principle, any derogation must be *justified* by the fact that the full application of any of these rights, as Art. 89(2) GDPR reads: “are likely to render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of the specific purposes” and that such derogations “are necessary for the fulfilment of those purposes”. Finally, pursuant to Art. 89(4), where multiple purposes are served by the processing of personal data, one of which falls within the scope of derogations for research as defined by Art. 89 GDPR, the processing falling out of that research scope may not benefit from the discussed research exemption.

All in all, it appears that the research exemption in the GDPR is quite undefined and leaves much space for interpretation by Member States. This may lead to an adverse effect on the scope of research that can be conducted in different Member States and may even impair the effective functioning of the desired European Research Area.[28]

Acknowledging the fact that *valid consent for research purposes* under the GDPR is a rather contested topic, modes of consent in a research context are still to be examined. In general, modes of consent within the meaning of research include: Specific, informed consent; Democratic consent; Dynamic consent management; Sectoral consent; Open/general/broad/blanket consent. [29] Broad consent necessitates a single affirmative action in order to allow the data to be utilised for research purposes in general, without the imposition of any strict temporal limitation. The

application of the broad consent notion to any further processing for research purposes may thus be said to be clashing with the principles of purpose limitation and storage limitation. As already outlined, arguably going against the spirit of the GDPR, with its lack of specificity, and in the context of the research exemption of the GDPR, Recital 33 reads that “[d]ata subjects should have the opportunity to give their consent only to certain areas of research or parts of research projects”.^[30]

On the other hand, whether bypassing the consent of the data subject, when applied correctly, relying on the *legitimate interest legal basis* instead for research purposes, has been subject to debates, too. ^[31]It has been argued that the interpretation of the Article 29 WP in their Opinion on legitimate interest creates such possibility, with regard to processing for research purposes, particularly regarding marketing research. The latter is echoed in Recital 47 of the GDPR, linking direct marketing and the legitimate interest legal basis, in which case the *balancing test* required would still necessitate “careful assessment including whether a data subject can reasonably expect at the time and in the context of the collection of the personal data that processing for that purpose may take place.” Furthermore, Recital 49 states that *network and information security and fraud prevention are also considered legitimate interests* for data controllers, to the extent strictly necessary and subject to a proportionate test. Essentially, processing data on the basis of legitimate interest is acceptable when there is a security concern regarding the company or the data subject, with this making total sense, since both the data controller and data subject should be concerned about such an issue. Yet, the link between research and the legitimate interest legal basis appears to be somewhat weak. Furthermore, the lack of experience with the legal basis and the rather unclear scope of the balancing test leads to a rather *high degree of legal uncertainty*, as the risk assessment must be conducted by the controller prior to the processing and any mistake, especially in the research context, may lead to serious negative consequences.

In fact, *the precise meaning of Art. 89(1) GDPR is largely debated in some countries*. One could argue that Member States should adopt specific legislation specifying their own required safeguards. Others defend that the same article imposes obligations for researchers, as controllers, to implement safeguards. Case law on safeguards for processing for scientific research purposes is overall very limited, both at the international and national levels. ^[32]At the same time, the highest international courts stress the important role of national law. The *European Court of Human Rights* has stated repeatedly that:

“[...] protection of [...] data is of fundamental importance to a person’s enjoyment of his or her right to respect for private life as guaranteed by Article 8 of the Convention. The domestic law must therefore afford

appropriate safeguards to prevent any such use of personal data as may be inconsistent with the guarantees of this Article [...]. The domestic law should notably ensure that such data are relevant and not excessive in relation to the purposes for which they are stored, and preserved in a form which permits identification of the data subjects for no longer than is required for the purpose for which those data are stored [...]. *The domestic law must also afford adequate guarantees that retained personal data are efficiently protected from misuse and abuse* [...]. The above considerations are especially valid as regards the protection of special categories of more sensitive data' [...] (emphasis added)". [33]

With due regard to the above, the project team that has drafted the *Study on the appropriate safeguards under Art. 89(1) GDPR for the processing of personal data for scientific research*, therefore argues that “the European Economic Area States shall adopt *national law specifying the safeguards* when personal data is used for scientific research for securing the rights and freedoms of data subjects and to limit any risks after due assessment”. [34] Nevertheless, in the meantime, as hard and soft law on the topic is evolving, prior to commencing a processing operation, the following questions must be assessed as a starting point:

- Are the requirements of Art. 89 GDPR met?
- Would the application of any right from which there is a derogation seriously compromise the purpose?
- Is the use of the derogation necessary and proportional for achieving the purpose?
- Are there any further requirements and/or derogations in EU or national law?
- Is the process and reasoning documented?

4.1.1 Data Protection by Design and by Default

The importance of GDPR in *Collaborative Research & Development demands a multilayered approach to data protection*. Compliance is required during the technological development stages within the given project, but also in terms of securing ethical guarantees to the protection of personal data of human participants within the timeframe of the implementation of the project and beyond its term. It is worthwhile to differentiate between the two types of compliance mechanisms.

Firstly, pursuant to the GDPR, privacy shall be secured both “by design and by default”. “*Privacy by design*” ensures “data protection through technology design”, i.e., data protection is best adhered to when it is integrated into the technology already during its development stage. “*Privacy by default*” refers to the requirement for the controller to implement appropriate technical and organisational measures for ensuring that “by default” only the data necessary for each specific purpose of the processing is processed. The obligation for data protection “by default” is closely interlinked with the one on data protection “by design”, and may thus be perceived only as a

substantiation of the latter, and this may be observed in the *Seven Foundational Principles of Privacy by Design* that have been developed and referred to by the European Union Agency for Network and Information Security (hereinafter "ENISA") in its report on "Privacy and Data Protection by Design – from policy to engineering", where guidance on engineering privacy, privacy design strategies, as well as privacy techniques, are outlined. The principles are summarised below, and are evidence that privacy-enhancing technologies as simply added components on top of existing systems are not panacea that could solve all privacy problems, but that *privacy embedded into design must be demanded as a preventive and proactive measure*.

- *Proactive not Reactive; Preventative not Remedial*: Characterised by proactive rather than reactive measures, the Privacy by Design approach anticipates and prevents privacy invasion prior to it taking place. In other words, it aims to prevent risks from materialising.
- *Privacy as the Default*: Privacy by Default means that as Privacy by Design is built into the system, no action is required on the part of the individual to protect their privacy. That is the reason to name it Privacy by Default, as even if an individual does nothing, their privacy remains intact, i.e., privacy within the given system is secured by default.
- *Privacy Embedded into Design*: Privacy is an integral component of the core functionality being delivered, as it is embedded into the design and architecture of IT systems, and business practices from their onset, and are thus not bolted on as an add-on, post-factum.
- *Full Functionality – Positive-Sum, not Zero-Sum*: Privacy by Design aims to demonstrate that it is possible, as well as more desirable, to seek to accommodate all legitimate interests and objectives in a positive-sum manner, without unnecessary trade-offs. For instance, that it is both possible and necessary to encompass both privacy and security.
- *End-to-End Security – Lifecycle Protection*: Privacy by Design, having been embedded into the system prior to the first element of information being collected, secures lifecycle management of information, end-to-end, with strong security measures in place, meaning that data is securely retained, and then securely destroyed at the end of the process, in a timely manner.
- *Visibility and Transparency*: The component parts and operations of the respective technology involved, and the given business practice, remain visible and transparent, to both users and providers alike.
- *Respect for User Privacy*: Maintaining a user-centric approach, architects and operators are to be safeguarding strong privacy defaults, appropriate notice, and empowering user-friendly options.

4.1.2 Ensuring Lawfulness of Data Sharing

As a summary, an attempt to provide a simplified overview of the questions that need to be answered in order to ensure the lawfulness of data sharing is herewith provided. [14] Firstly, it must be verified if the given datasets that are subjected to data sharing include personal data. If they do not, data protection rules are not applicable, e.g., in the case when data sharing concerns anonymised data. However, in case of the affirmative, when personal data is contained in the datasets, even when pseudonymised, data protection rules are still applicable. Secondly, it must be analysed if special categories of data are to be subjected to data sharing, in which case, the grounds which allow for the legal processing must cover both the elements of the catalogue of the legal grounds for the processing pursuant to Art. 6, and one of the exceptions to the prohibition of processing special categories of data foreseen by Art. 9. If there are no special categories of data included in the given dataset, the processing must be based on one of the legal bases from Art. 6. Thirdly, any type of processing must be in compliance with the principles of processing stemming from Art. 5. This is crucial, as the principles, and their content is often interpreted broadly, could lead to the limitation of data sharing (e.g., data minimisation). Fourthly, it is necessary to ensure that the rights of data subjects are respected throughout the entire processing. From the catalogue of information that needs to be provided to the data subject on the recipients of their data, to right of data rectification or erasure, and depending on the legal bases on which the processing is taking place, the relevant rights need to be respected. Finally, on instances of international data transfers, it is necessary to ensure that the relevant legal bases for them are covered. The possibilities concerning the types of legal bases on which it would be possible to base such transfers would depend on, e.g., which third-country is involved, and on whether transfers are taking place within an organisation or between various enterprises.

In the context of DATAMITE, it has been ensured that all applicable to the Project provisions have been abide by and safeguarded. LIF has not only explained the GDPR applicability in both D4.5, but it has also held separate online sessions with all six Pilots prior to submitting the said report, and provided templates to be filled-in, in order for the types of data sharing and the content of the datasets to be clearly identified. Following the official submission of D4.6, LIF shall organise another recap sessions with all involved partner organisations, thereby reconfirming the applicable implications, thus also ensuring the continuity of best practices among partners also post-project.

5 Additional Applicable Legal & Ethics Sources

5.1 The EU Artificial Intelligence Act (EU AI Act) & The Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI

D4.5 has already explained in detail what different roles and obligations exist pursuant to the European Union Artificial Intelligence Act (hereinafter “EU AI Act”, or “AI Act”) [19], but also Ethics-wise Trustworthiness [13], namely, those related to developers and deployers, as well as the risk assessment methodology concerning different levels of risks, namely, “unacceptable” risk, “high-risk”, “limited risk”, “minimal”, etc. What is more, the previous Report has also provided a self-assessment tool to be utilised whenever the provisions in question are applicable.

In the case of DATAMITE, and its six Pilots, the only instance that may be applicable in that regard concerns the role and associated obligations of deployers. Of course, this shall be finally re-confirmed also within the context of the functional & non-functional requirements review. Yet, in general terms, it shall be recalled that datasets are still to always adhere to the best possible practices, irrespective of the given role (developer/provider) or the risk classification, or even of the presence or lack of AI at all. Following this logic, Art. 10., despite being said to relate to the handling of high-risk AI systems, specifically, should still be adhered to in any context, thereby allowing for a best-practices approach. In addition, it needs to be ensured that, should respective datasets be utilised for post-project purposes, falling under any of the categories requiring high vigilance, those need to be compliant already from the onset. The following paragraph thus avails some thoughts in the context of data governance, accuracy, and robustness, as Art. 10 EU AI Act.

Pursuant to the framework of Art. 10 on “Data and Data Governance”, high-quality data sets for training, validation, and testing must be ensured. The data sets are to be managed properly, taking into account factors like data collection processes, data preparation, potential biases, and data gaps. Relevancy and representativeness of the data sets must be ensured, too, and the same data are to be free of any error. Quality criteria are then referred to in paragraphs 2 to 5. In cases when AI systems are developed without using techniques involving the training of AI models, the provisions of paragraphs 2 to 5 apply only to the testing data sets. Paragraph 2 explains that the data governance and management practices shall be implemented regarding the training, validation and testing of datasets, and that the same shall concern: relevant data

choices; data collection processes and the origin of data, and in the case of personal data, the original purpose of the data collection; relevant data-protection processing operations, e.g., annotation, labelling, cleaning, updating, enrichment and aggregation; an assessment of the availability, quantity and suitability of the data sets that are needed; examination against any possible biases that may affect the health and safety of persons, have a negative impact on fundamental rights, or lead to discrimination, particularly where data outputs influence inputs for future operations; ensuring appropriate measures for detection, prevention and mitigation of possible biases. Monitoring for the identification of any relevant data gaps or shortcomings that may prevent compliance with the AI Act is also to be ensured, including the addressing of those gaps and shortcomings. Furthermore, paragraph 4 mandates that data sets are to take into account the characteristics or elements that are particular to the given geographical, contextual, behavioural or functional setting within which the AI element is being used. Paragraph 5 regulates scenarios that strictly necessitate, for the purposes of ensuring bias detection and correction, the processing of special categories of personal data, subject to appropriate safeguards for the fundamental rights and freedoms of natural persons.

Bias and Discrimination: Art. 9(1) GDPR sets a prohibition on data controllers to *not process special category of data unless an exception applies*, as provided by Art.9(2), and subject to the safeguards provided by Art. 9(3). On the other hand, Art. 10(5) EU AI Act postulates in a slightly conflicting manner that if considered strictly necessary for the purposes of ensuring bias monitoring, namely, bias detection and correction (i.e., “de-biasing”), with regard to high-risk AI systems, the providers of such systems may be *allowed by exception to process special categories of personal data referred to in Art.9(1) GDPR*. Art.10(5) EU AI Act goes further in mandating *appropriate safeguards*. In similar cases, organisations may thus request the individual’s *explicit consent* for the processing of the given sensitive data. However, in many situations, obtaining valid consent from an individual is not feasible. Another possible exception to the general rule is that there exists *a requirement by Union or Member State Law*. However, national laws in Europe do not provide for an exception enabling the processing of sensitive data for AI de-biasing. Yet, the exception contained in the EU AI Act does constitute *European Union Law within the meaning of the GDPR*. Moreover, the EU AI Act’s exception is *in the public interest*, as defined by Article 9(2)(g) GDPR. Art. 9 (2)(g) GDPR thus allows for an exception “for reasons of substantial public interest”, e.g., fighting discrimination, based on “Union or Member State Law”, e.g., the EU AI Act. However, for justification to be applicable, *three conditions need to be met*: the given law must be proportionate to the aim pursued; it must respect the core aspects of the

right to data protection; as well as to avail suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subject. [7] [13]

5.2 Directive on Measures for a High Common Level of Cybersecurity (NIS 2)

NIS2 Directive [11] aims at strengthening cybersecurity across the EU, as well as at improving the functioning of the EU's internal market by requiring MSs to adopt national strategies, designate relevant authorities and computer security incident response teams, as well as to enforce cybersecurity risk-management and report obligations for key entities, promote information sharing, and ensure proper supervision and enforcement.

The Directive outlines several sectors considered crucial for the functioning of the economy and society, and the same are classified into two main categories, namely, sectors of high criticality (Annex I of NIS 2) & other critical sectors (Annex II of NIS 2). While “high criticality sectors” include, e.g., energy, digital infrastructure, transport, space, health, public administration, drinking water, banking, financial markets infrastructure, wastewater, ICT services management (B2B), “other critical sectors” refer to manufacture, production and distribution of chemicals, manufacturing, research, postal and courier services, waste management, production, processing and distribution of food, digital providers. Entities within the listed sectors are then subject to categorisation depending on their size, sector or criticality, and are either classified as “essential entities” or “important entities”. Furthermore, the Directive applies to public or private entities of a type referred to in its Annex I or II, which qualify as (1) medium-sized enterprises or (2) exceed the ceilings for medium-sized enterprises and which provide their services or carry out their activities within the Union. Concerning the size-cap, medium-sized enterprises employ fewer than 250 persons and have an annual turnover not exceeding EUR 50 million, and/or an annual balance sheet total not exceeding EUR 43 million.

All in all, irrespective of the type of entity, both essential and important ones are obliged to meet common criteria, e.g., implement risk management measures, report significant cybersecurity incidents, with essential entities being subject to both ex-ante (prior to a cybersecurity accident) & ex-post (following a cybersecurity accident) supervision, while important entities to ex-post supervision only. D4.5 has outlined in detailed what obligations such entities have to meet.

There are several instances on which, NIS 2 has a high likelihood of stricto sensu applicability within the DATAMITE Pilot Organisations, e.g., in the context of the energy sector, digital

infrastructure, but also to offering data to data service providers and data spaces. Subject also to national implementation and the cap thresholds, different entities shall consult further the specificities of the matter. Nevertheless, even when in doubt of the applicability, organisations shall always strive for the best practices approach, by implementing the following cybersecurity risk-management measures, at minimum.

- Policies on risk analysis and information system security.
- Incident handling.
- Business continuity, including backup management, disaster recovery, and crisis management.
- Supply chain security, addressing security aspects between entities and their suppliers or service providers.
- Security in network and information systems acquisition, development, and maintenance, covering vulnerability handling and disclosure.
- Policies and procedures to assess the effectiveness of cybersecurity risk-management measures.
- Basic cyber hygiene practices and cybersecurity training.
- Policies and procedures regarding the use of cryptography and encryption, as appropriate.
- Human resources security, access control policies, and asset management.
- Use of multi-factor authentication, continuous authentication solutions, secure voice, video, and text communications, and secured emergency communication systems within the entity, as needed.

In addition, the previous Report has also provided a self-assessment tool to be utilised for a good cyber-hygiene.

5.3 Intellectual Property Rights

Whilst D4.5 has explored the Trade Secrets Directive, D6.5 due at the end of M36 is dedicated to analysing further in more detail the intellectual property rights (hereinafter “IPR”) tenets, as well as to outlining the exploitation pathways, based also on the commenced interviews with partners during the last Plenary Meeting in Valencia that took place in M34. LIF and AUSTRALO has also conducted a webinar presenting all core IPR principles.

6 Further Ethical Dimensions

6.1 Human Participation and Personal Data

The DATAMITE Partners have been advised that any involvement of natural persons outside the Consortium regarding, e.g., the validation of project-related outputs, which falls within the scope of voluntary research participation for the collection of feedback, requires additional attention and effort, such as providing informed consent. For this reason, relevant documentation and templates have been ongoingly prepared and shall be reconfirmed to each Pilot Partner during the extra online sessions that LIF is envisaging after the submission of D4.6. The prepared set of documentation to be finally disseminated, and which may be further utilised for different Horizon Europe purposes in a tailored manner, includes: Data Protection Impact Assessment (hereinafter “DPIA”); Incidental Findings Policy; Recruitment Policy; Information Sheet; Informed Consent; Non-Disclosure Agreement. The general rules that remain binding and which have influenced the rationale behind the required steps are as follows.

- Participation in research should always be voluntary, free from coercion or undue influence. Efforts should be taken to minimise power imbalances, considering the participants’ pre-existing relationships with those conducting the validation activities.
- The Consent Form must be completed with specific activity details and provided to participants in writing before the activity begins, along with an oral explanation of their rights.
- Participants should always have the right to withdraw from participation without facing negative consequences. They should be informed whether data already gathered before withdrawal is going to be retained, to what extent, as well as what the legal basis for this retention is.
- Participants must receive comprehensive and understandable information about their engagement, including their expected input and how it is going to be collected, the purposes for which it is going to be used, any third parties it may be shared with, and details about the venue, duration, and organisers of the activity. All these details should be included in the templated Information Sheet. The Incidental Findings Policy should also be communicated to participants before the activity begins.
- The principles of fairness, respect for human dignity, and non-discrimination should underlie all research activities. Confidentiality must be ensured regarding data gathered

through research activities involving external participants, using pseudonymization or anonymisation techniques whenever possible. Therefore, any association of identifiable individuals with their provided input must be duly justified, with a balancing assessment performed between the rights of individuals and the legitimate interest of the given consortium conducting the validation.

- The possibility to opt out of further contact related to the research activity should be effectively communicated to and provided to participants.

In general, it has been verified that no physical and/or psychological harm is associated with the conduct of validation activities for the DATAMITE Project, and neither are individuals from vulnerable groups expected to take part in the activities.

On the other hand, there are ethical guarantees to the protection of personal data of participants within the Project activities that need to be adhered to, and the same are composed of two main objectives – providing context to the already applicable legal framework (as under the GDPR section), but also complementing the existing legal provisions in cases where they may not be applicable, or where there might be uncertainty about their execution. The following list has thus been inspired by the Ethics and Data Protection guidance provided by the European Commission in 2021. [19]

- A mapping of personal data processing activities across the Consortium shall be performed within the preparation of the dedicated Data Management Plan (final v. of the said Report is due in March 2026, and regular updates are to be made of the information provided, alongside ad hoc ones, should unforeseen circumstances arise. Any planned secondary use of data shall be duly notified to allow for examining the origins and lawfulness of processing previously collected data.
- In addition to giving due consideration to the principles of data minimisation and purpose limitation of personal data processing, the identification of data subjects and the types of personal data to be collected is to be conducted in advance, during the preparatory stage of organising the given activity involving human subjects.
- On instances when there is a risk of affecting an individual's rights due to the type of data to be gathered, its volume, and/or the consequences that might be related to the individual providing it when already the principles of minimisation and purpose limitation are complied with, a DPIA shall be carried out pursuant to Art. 35. Unless a justification is

provided for the need to identify the authorship of the statements received, feedback forms or other participant input should be collected in anonymised versions.

- Participation documentation is to always be collected separately from research inputs. Whilst consent forms shall always constitute a stand-alone document of which the participant can receive a copy if requested, the Information Sheet shall always be available for their usage.
- External participants may only be engaged in activities after having provided informed consent, with the purpose and scope of their involvement priorly communicated in a language understandable to them, in a comprehensible manner, as well as with an indication of any ensuing risks and/or benefits from their participation, along with their data subject rights.
- Contact details of respective DPOs or other relevant representatives of partners undertaking the roles of data processor / data controller within the activities conducted, shall be communicated to research participants as recourse for exercising their data subjects' rights.
- Personal data collected is to always be stored securely by ensuring appropriate technical and organizational measures are taken for the preservation from any potential breaches. Access to repositories containing information is to always be limited on a need-to-know basis to partners responsible for the organisation of the concrete activity. Consecutive audits shall be conducted regularly to ensure the accuracy and up-to-datedness of data stored. No longer needed data shall be securely disposed of, and digital entries shall be deleted. As per the usual standard in other similar projects, and pursuant to data retention regulations, data shall be stored for no more than 5 years after the final payment to the project consortium members, which is the maximum period associated with external audits.

7 New European Strategy for Data

7.1 The Views of the DATAMITE Consortium

In view of the Open Consultation on the forthcoming New European Strategy for Data, launched during the second quarter of 2025, and which is now closed, DATAMITE has summarised its observations and recommendations to serve as guiding points when deciding on the pillars of the New Strategy. As the EC is proposing to base the forthcoming Data Union Strategy on the below-referenced three main pillars, the same have been discussed from the point of experience within the DATAMITE Consortium, which is now looking forward to observing how the data sharing landscape is evolving over time in that regard. The official Policy Brief may be found in Zenodo.

- Concerning Pillar I – *Improving and Facilitating Secure Private and Public Data Sharing* – the following points for action need to be addressed: Clear data governance frameworks that define roles, responsibilities, and access rights for all stakeholders; Interoperability-by-design through common standards and reference architectures, developed collaboratively but flexibly recognising national and regional specificities; Support for secure, value-driven data exchange, including mechanisms for trusted anonymisation and cybersecurity; In a check & balances manner, data spaces themselves, and not only technology providers, shall be responsible for ensuring/certifying that participants share data in a legally and ethically compliant manner; Common Data Monetization Framework EU-wide is needed, including further unification towards a common EU-wide regulatory approach.
- Concerning Pillar II – *Simplifying the Regulatory Regime, Improving Consistency, and Fostering Application* – the following points for action need to be addressed: Light-touch, principle-based regulation, focused on key outcomes like transparency, accountability, and interoperability; Promote and develop regulatory sandboxes and Pilot-friendly frameworks that allow different stakeholders to test data-sharing models in real conditions before scaling; Soft law instruments, e.g.: guidelines; codes of conduct; or common reference architectures – co-created with the sector and updated iteratively. Ready-to-use templates for organisations, elaborating on and harmonising the efforts at national level, shall also be encouraged, as well as the creation of straightforward and easy to apply resources, including checklists, practical guidelines for compliance in action, etc; Measures for enhancing consistency of the application and enforcement by national

authorities, e.g.: collection of positions by national authorities on priority issues taken in national guidance and decisions, including court judgements, thus producing publications in a “case law” manner, thereby assisting organisations in understanding concrete positions taken concerning interpretation; ongoing monitoring to further complement guidelines, to ensure effectiveness and consistent application including through reviews of the same, as well as through targeted coordinated enforcement actions and strategies; continued effort in aligning domestic and EU-level guidance in cases of identified inconsistencies; develop common practices, methodologies, tools and common actions for greater harmonisation of enforcement; Cross-Regulatory Measures to Improve Consistency, e.g.: preparing joint guidelines together with regulators, as deemed appropriate, in order to ensure consistency in the application of different legal frameworks; enabling effective and structured cooperation amongst regulators to exchange experience and to address legal and practical challenges in cross-regulatory cooperation on concrete cases; fostering proactively meetings between domestic regulators and relevant EU bodies, as deemed relevant. The above-referenced measures shall reduce the overall complexity of regulations, currently constituting more of a hurdle for smaller actors in terms of ensuring compliance, as usually only big companies have in-house lawyers. As many SMEs do not understand or are oftentimes not even aware of legal & ethics requirements, this shall thus enable all stakeholders, including SMEs, to identify their obligations and ensure compliance. On the other hand, the proposed measures shall also improve overall consistency, application, as well as enforcement of the regulatory framework.

- Concerning Pillar III – *Accelerating the Development of New Systems and Applications* – the following points for action need to be addressed: Avoid mandates of specific platforms or architectures which risk locking stakeholders into rigid or costly solutions; Support reference frameworks that allow diverse systems to interconnect, rather than replace what works locally; Encourage the development of open APIs, common data models, and shared ontologies which make it easier to build interoperable apps and services.

8 Conclusions

D4.6 has not only reflected the technological developments within the DATAMITE project from a legal and ethical point of view, but the document has also elaborated on sectoral legislation and the overall potential of new upcoming hard and soft laws. In addition, the tailored guidelines per Pilots have been revised and updated accordingly since the previous version of the report (D4.5). Furthermore, in comparison to D4.5, which has mainly outlined the applicable roles and duties within the data sharing process, D4.6 has delved deeper into examining further the different concepts and principles, thereby providing a more analytical and revised approach.

The vital importance of creating an environment that supports data-driven innovation – alongside upholding transparency, accountability and privacy, and which has been clearly underscored by the demonstrated EU’s commitment to promoting data sharing through the legislative initiatives – has also been discussed. As has been witnessed, these regulatory efforts address challenges related to data access, interoperability and fairness, thereby pursuing the fostering of prosperity and inclusiveness across digital and data markets Europe-wide.

Even though numerous gaps exist currently, calling for regulatory intervention, one critical issue seems to persist, and that is regarding B2B data sharing. By discussing the scarcity of B2B data-sharing initiatives that underscores the need for focused attention and strategic interventions for unlocking the full potential of data-driven collaboration among businesses, D4.6 has provided actionable strategies for stakeholders.

All in all, the generation of D4.6, as well as the Definition of the Legal & Ethical Requirements that are being shared separately and shortly thereafter, have been substantially relied upon the outcomes of D1.4 Requirements and Architecture (M30), D2.4 Data Sharing and Sovereignty Mechanisms (M33), as well as the questions that have been re-confirmed with respective Pilot and Technical Partners.

What does D4.6 (submitted in November 2025) cover to complement the former D4.5?

- Further in-depth analysis of the overall regulatory framework.
- Review of additional sectoral-related aspects.
- Updated revisions of applicability to Pilots.
- High-level comparative overview of the Framework (data types, pro-sharing objectives, tools).

What are the subsequent steps ahead (submitted/conducted in January 2026)?

- ~ 200 Functional & Non-Functional Requirements Rulebook Methodology (MoSCoW).
- Pilot Documentation as per Section 6.
- Wrap-Up Guidance and Q&A Webinar Pilots (Framework & Documentation).
- Wrap-Up Guidance and Q&A Technical Partners (Framework & finalised Appendix A).

9 References

REGULATORY FRAMEWORK:

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[6] Regulation (EU) 2018/1807 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 November 2018 on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data in the European Union (Free Flow of Non-Personal Data Regulation) [2018] OJ L 303 <<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32018R1807>> accessed on 20 October 2025

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[9] Directive (EU) 2019/944 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on common rules for the internal market for electricity and amending Directive 2012/27/EU (recast) (Common Rules for the Internal Market for Electricity) [2019] <<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/944/2024-07-16/eng#:~:text=This%20Directive%20establishes%20common%20rules%20for%20the%20gene>>

[ration%2C,competitive%2C%20consumer-centred%2C%20flexible%2C%20fair%20and%20transparent%20electricity%20market](#) accessed on 20 October 2025.

[10] Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2023/1162 of 6 June 2023 on interoperability requirements and non-discriminatory and transparent procedures for access to metering and consumption data (Electricity Metering and Consumption Data Interoperability Regulation) [2023] <<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32023R1162>> accessed on 20 October 2025

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Appendix A: Definition of Legal & Ethical Requirements to the DATAMITE Tools

Req. ID	Requirement Description	Actor	Source	Category	Requirement Type	Priority
Text	Text	Text	Text	Text	Text	Text